

raisd

Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced

www.raisd-h2020.eu

D7.2 Cross-pilot workshop Reports

Lead partner: CESIE, Italy

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822688.

The information and views set out in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Document Information

Grant Agreement #:	822688
Project Title:	Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced
Project Acronym:	RAISD
Project Start Date:	1 st February, 2019
Related work package:	WP7 Cross-analysis
Deliverable:	D7.2 Cross-pilot workshop reports
Related task(s):	Task 7.2 Organisation of cross-pilot exchange workshops
Lead Organisation:	CESIE
Submission date:	Month 32
Dissemination Level:	Public

History

Date	Submitted by	Reviewed by	Version (Notes)
06/11/2020	CESIE	UCM, UH	Planning V.0
16/11/2020	CESIE	All	Planning approval V0
09/12/2020	CESIE	All	V1.1 (setting actual dates)
15/03/2021	CESIE	UCM, Menedék, UH, AU	Reporting V1
30/03/2021	CESIE	All	Approval V1
16/07/2021	CESIE	All	Reporting V2
22/07/2021	UCM	CESIE	Approval V2
24/01/2022	CESIE	UCM, UH	Reporting V3
26/01/2022	UCM, UH	CESIE	Approval V3

This Report is published under an [Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license [CC BY-SA].

www.raisd-h2020.eu

Del.7.2 Cross-pilot workshop Report [03/2021]

Coordinator contact: Dr. Rubén Fuentes-Fernández | Universidad Complutense de Madrid | Calle del Profesor José García Santesmases, 9. Ciudad Universitaria 28040 MADRID, Spain.
t: +34/ 91 394 7548 | e: rfuentes@ucm.es | w: www.ucm.es , grasia.fdi.ucm.es

Table of content

Glossary.....	4
Introduction.....	5
Task 7.2 Cross-pilot workshop (n.1).....	7
Strengths.....	9
Weaknesses	12
Opportunities.....	14
Threats	16
Evaluation by participants.....	17
Task 7.2 Cross-pilot workshop (n.2).....	18
Who	20
Why.....	22
What	25
hoW	28
Task 7.2 Cross-pilot workshop (n.3).....	31
Retrospective Feed-back.....	33
Feed-forward Recommendations	36
Conclusions	37
- Annex 1 -	39
SWOT Analyses by local Action-Research Units	40
Spain.....	41
Italy.....	52
Finland.....	54
Hungary.....	57
Turkey.....	59
Jordan.....	60
Lebanon.....	63

<i>About RAISD</i>	
<i>Call (part) identifier</i>	<i>H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2018</i>
<i>Topic</i>	<i>MIGRATION-08-2018 Addressing the challenge of forced displacement</i>
<i>Fixed EC Keywords</i>	<i>Globalisation, migration, interethnic relations</i>
<p><i>Forced displacement crises overcome societies and institutions all over the world. Pushed by the urgencies rather than events, solutions are frequently reactive, partial, and disregard some groups. The project 'Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced' (RAISD) aims at identifying highly Vulnerable Groups (VG) among these forcibly displaced people, analysing their specific needs, and finding suitable practices to address them. The concept of 'vulnerability context' considers the interplay between the features of these persons and their hosting communities, their interactions and experiences, and how different solutions for attention and inclusion affect them. As a result of this work, a methodology to carry out these studies will be developed. These goals are aligned with the call. They pursue characterizing these migrations and developing suitable aid strategies for them. The Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) frames the project. It proposes that all actors (including civil society) co-design actions, transversely integrates the gender perspective, and supports sustainability. Our research strategy will be based on methodological triangulation (i.e. the combined application of several methodologies). We will implement it through a specific participatory action research approach to fulfil the aim of undertaking advocacy-focused research, grounded in human rights and socio-ecological models. The team will work as a network of units in countries along migration routes. The units will promote the VG people' involvement, so they can speak with their own voices, gather information, and test practices. Work will rely on a tight integration of Social and Computer Sciences research. Automated learning and data mining will help to provide evidence-based recommendations, reducing a priori biases. A software tool will support collaboration, continuing previous H2020- funded RRI work.</i></p>	

The sole responsibility of this publication lies with the author.

The European Union is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Coordinator contact:

Dr. Rubén Fuentes-Fernández | Universidad Complutense de Madrid | Calle Profesor José García Santesmases, 9. Ciudad Universitaria 28040 MADRID, Spain.

t: +34/91 394 7548 | email: rfuentes@ucm.es | web site: www.ucm.es grasia.fdi.ucm.es

Glossary

ARU	Action Research Unit
EC	European Commission
FDP	Forcibly Displaced People / Person
HVG	Highly Vulnerable Group
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PRSF	Psychosocial Refugee Support Forum
RAISD	Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
RSS	Refugee Support System
TAIS	Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategy
VC	Vulnerability Context
VG	Vulnerable Group
WP	Work Package

Introduction

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) leads to empowered, responsible actors across Research and Innovation systems focusing on the need of co-creating research activities where all the relevant stakeholders play an active role in its definition, execution and evaluation (researchers, policymakers, businesses and innovators, CSOs, educators).¹

In this view, the three RAISD exchange-workshops were part of the local action research-agenda, aiming at gathering new insights on [“Tailored-Attention and Inclusion Practices” TAIS](#) processes in the different partner countries (Lebanon, Jordan, Turkey, Hungary, Finland, Italy and Spain) and to further facilitate the exchange between scientific and societal actors. Becoming part of a transformative action-research process rather than a one-off event, the workshops had the potential to practicing a more responsible research and innovation that requires that processes are²:

- **Diverse and inclusive:** involve early a wide range of actors and publics in R&I practice, deliberation, and decision-making to yield more useful and higher quality knowledge. This strengthens democracy and broadens sources of expertise, disciplines and perspectives.
- **Anticipative and reflective:** envision impacts and reflect on the underlying assumptions, values, and purposes to better understand how R&I shapes the future. This yields to valuable insights and increase our capacity to act on what we know.
- **Open and transparent:** communicate in a balanced, meaningful way methods, results, conclusions, and implications to enable public scrutiny and dialogue. This benefits the visibility and understanding of R&I.
- **Responsive and adaptive to change:** be able to modify modes of thought and behaviour, overarching organizational structures, in response to changing circumstances, knowledge, and perspectives. This aligns action with the needs expressed by stakeholders and publics.

This document provides an overview of “Task 7.2 Organisation of cross-pilot exchange workshops” that served as a platform for critical multi-Contexts and multi-Stakeholder perspectives, reflecting on assumptions, design, [evaluation-criteria](#) and actual implementation of the TAIS piloting rounds.

The [first exchange-workshop in January 2021](#) aimed at mapping internal and external systems; their impact within and around the Strategies’ contexts; Identifying potential anomalies by going back to initial assumptions, ideally deconstructing them; Investigating positive and negative effects rising from our action-research interventions.

The [second exchange workshop in June 2021](#) aimed at gathering constructive critical viewpoints on TAIS developments that would allow to further improve methodological aspects within and around the local attention and inclusion strategies for Highly Vulnerable Groups affected by forced displacement.

¹ Deblonde, M.: Responsible research and innovation - Building knowledge arenas for glocal sustainability research. *Journal of Responsible Innovation*. Routledge, 2015.

² RRI Tools: building a better relationship between science and society, RRI Toolkit. Retrieved from <https://rri-tools.eu/>, 20/01/2022.

The [third workshop in January 2022](#) aimed at gathering critical viewpoints on the three implemented TAIS piloting rounds in the different partner countries: Retrospective feedback followed by Feed-forward responsiveness.

The overall Cross-piloting Analysis Process involved a total of 110 Stakeholders, representing 33 ARU members from the seven national project contexts (Spain, Italy, Finland, Hungary, Turkey, Jordan, Lebanon).

Table 1. Attendees distribution by partner countries

Table 2. Attendees distribution by gender

The general RAISD evaluation framework highly benefitted from the organisation of this kind of multi-stakeholder workshops. Although the project’s initial design for this activity was to implement three international face-to-face workshops (each Action-Research Unit were to be represented by its Leader, one member of the local Vulnerable Groups, and another of the civil society or policy makers), due to the 2020/2021 Covid-19 pandemic travel limitations, the format of the cross-pilot exchange workshops had to change format (from in-presence to online), it actually permitted a much larger participation in terms of number of attendees and variety of stakeholders’ profiles.

raisd

Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced

www.raisd-h2020.eu

Task 7.2 Cross-pilot workshop (n.1)

- 20/01/2021 -

www.raisd-h2020.eu

Del.7.2 Cross-pilot workshop Report [03/2021]

Coordinator contact: Dr. Rubén Fuentes-Fernández | Universidad Complutense de Madrid | Calle del Profesor José García Santesmases, 9. Ciudad Universitaria 28040 MADRID, Spain.
t: +34/ 91 394 7548 | e: rfuentes@ucm.es | w: www.ucm.es , gracia.fdi.ucm.es

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822688.

TASK 7.2 Cross-pilot exchange workshop 1

The first Cross-Analysis workshop's discussion groups evolved around an initial SWOT Analysis and related relevant questions (see [Annex 1](#)):

- **Strengths** [internal]: What do you do well? What unique resources can you draw on?
- **Weaknesses**: What could you improve? Where do you have fewer resources than others?
- **Opportunities** [external]: What good opportunities are open to you and your VG? What trend/policies (internal and external to your institution) could you take advantage of? How can you turn your strengths into opportunities?
- **Threats** [external]: What trends/policies (internal and external to your institution) could hinder your TAIS success? What threats do your weaknesses exposes you?

Date and time	21/01/2021 10h00 to 12h30
Agenda	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – 10h00: TAIS overview [Plenary] ▪ 10h20: STRENGTHS [4 Breakout rooms] ▪ 10h40: WEAKNESSES [4 Breakout rooms] – 11h00: - break - ▪ 11h10: OPPORTUNITIES [4 Breakout rooms] ▪ 11h30: THREATS [4 Breakout rooms] ▪ 11h50: Discussion highlights [Plenary] – 12h15: Conclusions and closure
Participants	All partner countries were represented with total 33 participants (28 among ARU and AB members, plus 5 moderators. Gender balance: female 56%, male 44%).
Registration	https://zoom.us/meeting/register/tJMpdeuoqD4jE9FSI4r-vLDrCz2RoEsCN00w
Evaluation	https://forms.gle/pCUa2CjyYcySMBda8
Dissemination	https://www.facebook.com/raisd.h2020/posts/3611536448934583
Preparation	Among the pre-activities to the first exchange workshop, hold online the 21 st of January 2021, the seven Action Research Units performed a SWOT analysis of their local TAIS concepts and the just concluded piloting round in terms of Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats and potential future <i>Actionable Strategies</i> .

The results of this sessions are presented in the tables below.

Strengths

Minutes, breakout room "Strengths": Participants' input

What unexpected internal-STRENGTHS did you discover?

1. The TAIS are enabling people, beyond the beneficiaries, as those who participated in the design, running and evaluation process gained new capacities and knowledge on how to work with FDP and this specific VG.
2. The people/stakeholders engaged with the TAIS are very motivated, more than I would have expected in the beginning, appreciating the opportunity to exchange, share and spread knowledge, learn new ways of doing and getting into contact with new stakeholders.
3. The people engaged in our TAIS acknowledge the excellent planning of the strategies and actions, which made it possible to react in time and foresee the effects of the pandemics and other unexpected situations.
4. The possible future transfer effect of the TAIS, perfectly feasible according to the participants.
5. ARU's dedication and resilience during the different phases of TAIS, high flexibility, higher than expected.
6. The feeling of "doing good things", contributing to the reduction of vulnerabilities among participants.
7. Consolidating and extending the use of RRI within our countries and organisations.

"Strengths" of RAISD project are:

- I was more sensitive to fragile groups.
- Self-management became very clear.
- "Connect different parts with each other to implement the TAIS".
- "Having strong and universal training materials coming from the work between ARUs and researcher so it gathered the social with scientific".
- Raising the awareness as a constant process. It is something we took for granted, but it is a strength. Each communication process regarding the TAIS with stakeholders that not got involved (for different reasons) did had the information, and therefore awareness was raised.

Facilitators' minutes

Partner

UCM – Universidad Complutense de Madrid

In terms of **global strengths** of our TAIS brought up by the participants, the following ones were mentioned in the workshop:

- The TAIS are responding to strong real needs of FDP in participating countries, the TAIS are enabling people (beneficiaries, but also TAIS planners, trainers etc.) and empowering them to keep working and advancing, generating a snow ball effect. The TAIS are tailoring to FDP needs and contexts.
- Both beneficiaries and the people engaged in the organisation and practice of the TAIS contribute to building and sharing knowledge and spreading the word about the activities. The exchanges between stakeholders are fruitful and bring up new ideas and ways of doing things.
- The TAIS are actually contributing to reducing vulnerabilities and empowering FDP, especially women in the participating countries, which is the main objective of these strategies. Participants have a feeling we are really getting there, making effective contributions.

- We have highly committed people contributing to and collaborating with the TAIS, in the design, action and evaluation, especially the organisations that work with forcibly displaced people are very motivated, but also the universities and other stakeholders.
- The good planning of the TAIS is also a global strength that has allowed us to successfully face big challenges (such as Covid -19), anticipating and adapting to new scenarios and situations. In other words, the good planning has provided the TAIS with responsiveness and adaptation to change.
- The tools, strategies and practices within TAIS can be transferred to other areas and countries. Using online tools and formats in the TAIS is an important strength and makes the activities easy to transfer.
- Extending the use of RRI has been a positive point, it has brought new ways of exchanging ideas and collaborating among stakeholders, new ways of thinking to ARU and TAIS participants.
- Another strength related to the ARUS is their resilience, overcoming challenges and making changes.
- The TAIS are financed by the project and have resources from the partners and collaborating organisations (whereas many NGOs have difficulty financing their activities).

Areas of improvement were also discussed, in terms of potential future strengths that the participants feel would be important to our TAIS (and that are within our reach). These were the most relevant ones:

- Further and more frequent exchange of good practices between the partner countries. Spreading information and inspiring each other.
- Reaching more stakeholders, beyond the more engaged ones (NGOS, academy). Getting the word to more beneficiaries.
- Adapt the terminology used in RAISD to the terminology in the field. Use more general terminology, make it easier to understand for the stakeholders.
- Seek ways of making the TAIS sustainable in time (once the project finishes, the TAIS finish due to the lack of finance).

Also, interesting strengths related to each of the **TAIS in the diverse country contexts** were expressed by the participants, including the following, among others:

- In **Hungary**, in spite of the central government attacking FDP attention strategies, local government is being helpful. People from the NGOs are highly committed. Knowledge sharing and comparing insights about the same cases between social workers brought together interesting global information.
- In **Spain**, participants emphasized the tailored approach and the sustainability of the TAIS, as they engage all types of stakeholders. Also, the transfer of knowledge when experts that had worked with other types of publics gained expertise in the field of migration. The TAIS also fight against “machismo”, male domination, as women are under the focus of the activity and receive formation in traditionally (more) masculine fields, such as economics, business etc. This empowers and enables them.
- In **Finland**, the TAIS can be transferred anywhere anytime: the online community is easy to readapt to new contexts and beneficiaries and the childcare service is needed reception centres all over. Another strength was the use of already existing structures and the design of TAIS to complete their services (childcare service). Online implementation of one of the Finnish TAIS gives many opportunities for future action.

- **Italian** participants underlined the great motivation of the beneficiaries as the TAIS is responding to a strong need. Also, the importance of RRI as methodology principle, the change dynamics and roles, and exchanges at local level were mentioned. Through TAIS, the project is fostering RRI in our countries.
- In **Jordan**, the TAIS is covering important needs, as there is lack of support services for psychosocial assistance. Moreover, empowering FDP becomes self-support, Syrian refugees are enabled to provide their own support. The training is of great value for the beneficiaries, not only to the professional or educational ends, but also for their daily life. Also, the adaptability and acceptability of the TAIS are easy to measure, which is an important strength. RRI has also proved to be key for the Jordanian TAIS, Interchanges between stakeholders add value to the activity and participants learn new ways of doing things.
- **Turkish** participants focus on the gender issue in Turkey, which is still an important factor in general terms in the country, and particularly, within the local context of the TAIS and forcible displaced people. Therefore, the TAIS is contributing in drawing attention to gender balance, even beyond the specific migrations context. Also, the cultural and social aspects of the TAIS offer opportunities to the beneficiaries. In spite of the complex legal situation of Syrians in Turkey and the hostility of government, the TAIS benefits from the similarity of the Syrian culture (at least with some regions of Turkey). Also, Syrians are used to figuring out their own solutions in spite of the difficulties, resilient.
- In **Lebanon**, one of the strengths detected is that the TAIS improve the leadership and communication skills of the participants. The faculty in charge has strong teaching abilities and the TAIS has reached a good number of Syrian refugees, especially youth. As there are around 1,5 million of Syrians in Lebanon, there are challenges in terms of extending the information and TAIS to more beneficiaries. Spreading knowledge and generating snowball effect among beneficiaries are considered important strengths of the Lebanese TAIS, as well as sharing the good practices through an online platform.

Weaknesses

Minutes, breakout room "Weaknesses": Participants' input

What unexpected internal-WEAKNESSES did you discover?

- I learned that I do not know much about the studies done especially in the Scandinavian countries and I focused on research.
- Especially, during the Covid-19, significant number of team members had to struggle with conditions.
- Working with volunteers like ARUs for a long time.
- Need for second recruitment round (responsive strategy against digital-dropouts) was considered for another TAIS and might be also an issue for us. Also lack of budget for paying teachers/experts' participation.

Facilitators' minutes

Partner	University of Helsinki
---------	------------------------

Country-specific discussions:

- **Spain:** Not enough time to prepare the TAIS that needs plenty of co-operation between various stakeholders. Lack of time was also related to difficulties in creating feelings of community among people involved with TAIS (service providers and beneficiaries). The need to resort to digital communication has not helped in this. Moreover, in some cases service providers have lacked expertise on the crucial topic of TAIS: entrepreneurship and sometimes the planning and implementation of TAIS has had a too patronizing stance toward beneficiaries instead of a participatory approach. Further, some difficulties were recognized in relation to beneficiaries and taking into account their diversity and needs. Despite of trying to gather a group with similar interests and backgrounds, most of the participants seem to have diverging individual needs and the TAIS need to be adjusted according to them. In addition, there have been problems with the lack of ITC skills and lack of concrete possibilities for the target group.
- **Hungary:** Menedék has avoided plenty of problems because they are an organisation directly involved with potential beneficiaries. However, some weaknesses were recognized as well. One of them was an overall vagueness of the TAIS implementation. Since it is a process instead of a series of repeating cycles, there has been no time to test whether or not the goals have been achieved. Moreover, the timelines of the process are not clear and sometimes too ambitious. One recognized weakness was also a lack of resources and full-time people working with the project.
- **Jordan:** In Jordan, there has been difficulties in co-operation particularly with large organisations (NGOs). It has taken a lot of time to agree on various things and to exchange views and information. In Jordan, refugee camps are geographically far away from each other and people in the camps seem to have diverse interest and needs. The TAIS may have not been malleable enough in order to adjust it into changing surroundings. Moreover, potential stakeholders and beneficiaries have not been reached in the right time. Jordan team has had problems in finding committed enough people in their ARU.
- **Lebanon:** There has been gaps between researchers and some other stakeholders in their understanding about the TAIS and research methodologies involved in it. Thus, a common vocabulary may have been missing.

People from different disciplines and backgrounds have co-operated and there is thus a need to invest more time in reflecting the starting points and concepts thoroughly (similar point was raised by a Jordan representative as well). The co-operation with various NGOs has not been easy due to more or less hidden political agendas they tend to have.

- **Turkey:** A concern was raised whether the Turkish TAIS is able to take into account the deprived livelihoods of Syrian refugees. They are not recognized as citizens with a right to work, study and property.
- **Finland:** Several weaknesses were raised. First, there has been some recruitment problems in relation to beneficiaries (asylum seeking men). In this sense the TAIS has not been flexible enough in facing lockdown measures. This raises a question if the participant groups in Finnish TAIS are too small in numbers. Moreover, the other TAIS implemented in Finland (child-care services) requires quite a lot of resources and this was not taken enough into account when planning the TAIS. A key problem related to online forum is that it has not been integrated strongly enough into existing structure of service provision for asylum seekers. This is a serious threat to the sustainability of the TAIS.
- **Italy:** Similar to Finnish experiences, also in Italy there have been some recruitment problems. The potential beneficiaries are quite hard-to-reach in the first place and their participation has been quite fragmented in lengthy processes. Instead of being involved in trainings, several beneficiaries look for jobs to gain immediate benefits and to provide for their families. Moreover, lack of childcare might prevent some from participating.

Summarizing observations:

- One of the key challenges might stem from the organisation of the consortium and the whole project. The project includes people from various disciplines and professional backgrounds working in English. Further, project workers take the RAISD framework into their own contexts and deal with a great diversity of institutions and organisations in national languages. Finally, they need to communicate thoroughly with forcibly displaced people from heterogeneous backgrounds and operating in various languages. This complex structure includes several steps in which misunderstandings are more than likely. Some TAIS might be based on too hasty negotiations and too shallow mutual understandings.
- In many TAIS, there seems to be a lack of flexibility/malleability in case of surprises. There are always surprises. Of course, the severe lockdowns have put the TAIS under an extreme test in relation to malleability, but in many countries some unexpected needs and interests among the beneficiaries have been observed. Overall, in some cases it seems as if the deprived position and its consequences have not been predicted well enough.
- Strongly related to previous point, there seems to be challenges in finding a match between the TAIS and the right group of beneficiaries. In some cases, the so-called target group might be too broad lacking a focus, while in some cases too small excluding larger volumes and potentially interested people.

Opportunities

Minutes, breakout room "Opportunities": Participants' input

What unexpected external-OPPORTUNITIES did you discover?

- We influenced each other in different views as a result of the information exchange I made with various countries.
- Psychological support or other kinds of support are truly an opportunity for all members.
- Connection with NGOs and people who are working with refugees.
- Exchange amongst RAISD-partners is itself an unexplored /examined opportunity.

Facilitators' minutes

Partner	AU - Anadolu University
---------	-------------------------

In terms of opportunities of our TAIS shared by the participants, the following ones were mentioned in the workshop:

- The TAIS are constructed through a strong network of research team.
- Sustainability of the skills through TAIS can be seen as an opportunity.
- Local authorities' 'need to know' more on refugees is kind of an opportunity.
- There is a great need for some partners to reflect NGOs role and importance to the service.
- TAIS uniquely related with access to services do bring some potential opportunities according to partners.
- TAIS bring some kind of recognition to partners.
- TAIS put organisations in close contact with each other for a common purpose.
- TAIS did not only help partners to raise health literacy but also helped to scale up other literacies like technology and digital ones; delivery methods were also re-discovered.
- TAIS also underlined the importance of family literacies during the times of Covid-19.

Opportunities related to each of the TAIS in the diverse country contexts were expressed by the participants, including the following, among others:

- In **Hungary**, self-reflection on health can be considered as something new and rare, also a new angle. Also, it was mentioned that local authorities know very little about refugees so this can be an opportunity. Through NGO involvement, street level bureaucracy appears as great opportunity so vulnerable groups can get necessary services on ease.
- In **Spain**, trainings for entrepreneurship and various initiatives are bringing opportunities. Additionally, financial opportunities and tools need to be provided. Accordingly, vulnerable groups can create their own businesses. Synergies and interest between stakeholders bring new dimensions to those that have never worked together before; this is also shared by other partners.
- In **Finland**, municipalities and other organisations do not have the same level of experiences, TAIS bring various experiences to all participating stakeholders. It pushes municipalities to do more because of the engagement.
- **Italian** participants mentioned the importance of local community engagement and that getting experiences for all sides in the community is crucial.

- In **Jordan**, they experienced staff and people on how to develop materials brings an opportunity. Especially, the platform is really a connecting point for all stakeholders and sides. TAIS gives a chance to vulnerable people through its database on NGOs and their experiences. Refugees and students get unlimited access to the platform. The platform controls all services which help to connect refugees to the organisation so refugees feel safe. NGOs are really working with NGOs and all necessary funds do also come from regional and international funds for health, education and others.
- **Turkish** participants underline local authorities' active involvement as a great opportunity; they are the ones who makes the decisions. To have real effect and change, the involvement of local actors is a need. At the same time, TAIS connect opposing sides for a common good related with vulnerable groups.
- In **Lebanon**, university becomes more supportive and according to its role and its services, society's all members can make their decisions. TAIS also allows to share best practices. It allows networking and shapes things as "lego-making" so stakeholders take necessary practices. In addition, building a glossary of language was an opportunity.

Threats

Minutes, breakout room “Threats”: Participants’ input	
<p>What unexpected external-THREATS did you discover?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ I came to the conclusion that intensive work with local administration and university is paramount to impact on the vulnerable groups. Only in this way can be fought against the negative impact of experiencing discrimination. ▪ Digital world and screen-connections became overwhelmingly heavy. ▪ Covid-19 financial support to ensure the TAIS sustainability is bigger than first considered. 	
Facilitators’ minutes	
Partner	Menedék – Hungarian Association for Migrants
<p>The threats identified can be grouped in four main areas:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. THE EFFECTS OF THE PANDEMIC [Hungary, Jordan, Italy] <p>Lockdowns make movement difficult – both for beneficiaries and service providers in TAISes as well as for researchers.</p> <p>Shifting to online communication is difficult:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ problems with IT equipment and Internet access ▪ problems with IT literacy 2. ECONOMIC, POLITICAL, AND LEGAL CHANGES – INSTABILITY [Lebanon, Jordan, Spain] <p>These changes can occur on both national and local level as well as in regard to particular institutions. Some examples: a national economic and political crisis; a substantial change of the national asylum law; a change of the university’s leadership and governance structure; a change in the refugee population/community.</p> 3. CONFLICTING INTERESTS OF PARTIES INVOLVED/AFFECTED [Turkey, Hungary, Italy] <p>Policy goals and implementation opportunities often collide – local interests may differ from societal needs or there is a conflict between national and local policies and politics. Communities hosting refugees become increasingly polarized. Locals may feel that they are “left behind” when programmes and services targeting refugees are introduced. Refugees are not listened to, local press is not interested in their problems.</p> 4. SUSTAINABILITY [Finland, Jordan] <p>It is difficult to engage other institutions for the TAIS implementation. Longer term commitment of ARU and TAIS members is problematic – they are involved on a voluntary basis, their resources are limited. The TAIS may become as a substitute for missing or dysfunctional services and policies without being mainstreamed into the system. Once the project is over, the service gap may become even wider – this raises an ethical question too.</p> 	

Evaluation by participants

What did you learn from other TAISs that might help to improve your own Inclusion Strategy implementation?

New insights?

- Spreading the word about our TAIS. Refresh contingency plans in case we miss beneficiaries. Plans for extending the TAIS to potential new beneficiaries. More informal discussion and updates about the TAIS within our team.
- Absolutely, I learned a lot of information. The path followed and the solutions produced in different countries improved my thinking.
- Having a chance to benefit from self-reflections and develop health literacy skills.
- CESIE (Italian) recruitment model.

What is your critical perspective on how your TAIS is progressing?

- Adequate progress, there is some room for improvements.
- It was a positive and continuous meeting. I hope I will have the opportunity to meet these valuable academicians at Anadolu University. I hope they will come to our country.
- We will try to overcome screen-based meetings and establish mainly on face-to face if conditions allow.
- Positive, but Covid-19 make a lot of uncertainty. Also, the small number of participants worries me.

What actions and measures are needed to further improve your TAIS implementation process?

- Constant follow-up, listening to all team members, especially those who work closely with the beneficiaries.
- There should be more training and mutual information exchange. In addition, comprehensive relations with local governments and local media should be established.
- To take necessary precautions and preparations for Covid-19 process for having face to face processes.

Recommendations for Partners:

- Keep making contingency plans and schedule activities online due to the changing effects of Covid-19.
- Adding health service dimensions to the pilots.
- Creating synergies and interest from stakeholders must be materialised in practical support for the TAIS.
- Connecting different parts with each other to implement the TAIS.
- Having strong and universal training materials coming from the work between ARUs and researchers, so it gathered the social with the scientific.
- Raising the awareness as a constant process.
- Providing information on innovativeness and sustainability of the TAISs. These notions could constitute the themes for the discussions and provide valuable material in "WP7_Cross Analysis" to strengthen the evaluation framework. These quite important aspects are not included in the process and outcome evaluation.
- Elaborating (in-depth analysis) of those issues that came up frequently during the SWOT exercise.
- Sharing good practices that help overcoming the difficulties.
- Discussing ways of better incorporation/involvement of refugee communities.

raisd

Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced

www.raisd-h2020.eu

Task 7.2 Cross-pilot workshop (n.2)

- 10/06/2021 -

www.raisd-h2020.eu

Del.7.2 Cross-pilot workshop Report [03/2021]

Coordinator contact: Dr. Rubén Fuentes-Fernández | Universidad Complutense de Madrid | Calle del Profesor José García Santesmases, 9. Ciudad Universitaria 28040 MADRID, Spain.
t: +34/ 91 394 7548 | e: rfuentes@ucm.es | w: www.ucm.es , grasia.fdi.ucm.es

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822688.

TASK 7.2 Cross-pilot exchange workshop 2

The second Cross-Analysis Workshop discussion groups evolved around the “4W Questions”:

- **Who** is part of the TAIS? (involvement HVG and ARU; TAIS collaborations: Stakeholders and Networks).
- **Why** did you decide for that specific TAIS? (needs, relevance, criteria, assessment methods and practices).
- **What** does the TAIS offer? (what type of new, innovative and responsive activities/service is provided).
- **hoW** did you design and implement the TAIS? (methodology: assumptions, adjustments, sustainability).

Date and time	Thursday 10/06/2021, 09h30 to 12h30 [CET time].
Agenda	09h30: Welcome and tour de table 10h00: Who? 10h30: Why? >>> 11h00 Break 11h15: What? 11h45: hoW? 12h15 Plenary_Conclusions 12h30 Closure
Participants	All partner countries were represented with total 51 participants (42 among ARU and AB members, plus 5 moderators, 4 minute-takers Gender balance: female 60%, male 40%).
Registration	https://zoom.us/meeting/register/tJYqdu2ppzwtG9TGNVAK3SnRAnblmfiTEeUU
Dissemination	https://www.facebook.com/raisd.h2020/posts/4001316109956613
<i>Moderators</i>	
4W	Questions
WHO	<i>UNIMED</i>
WHY	<i>University of Helsinki</i>
WHAT	<i>Menedék – Hungarian Association for Migrants</i>
hoW	<i>Universidad Complutense de Madrid</i>

The results of this sessions are presented in the tables below.

Who

WHO	Who is part of the TAIS? (involvement HVG and ARU; TAIS collaborations: Stakeholders and Networks)
<i>Moderator</i>	<i>UNIMED Mediterranean Universities Union</i>

Minutes, breakout room “Who”

ROOM 1

- Italy: Vulnerable women, mainly Western African countries (HVG). Training in reception centre. Level of vulnerability even higher, women not able to physically reach the office (more vulnerable, health, mental health issues). Close contact with the reception centre, training in the living room.
- Hungary: Enable citizenship to work with TAIS. No centre, integration programmes, no language courses, homeless. NGOs but not trained. Creating profiles of vulnerability (typical stories).
- Jordan: Psychological problems, people living with a disability. Need for psychological support. Adaptation to Covid-19 situation, no communication tools.
- Finland: Multilingual training for young men staying in reception centres > recruited through RED CROSS+ working in Children clubs in Helsinki reception centres. From September to November, daily activity for Asylum seekers.
- Spain: Group of 6 women from sub-Saharan countries, many victims of traffic or sexual violence with children/elderly responsibilities. Focus on microfinance, workshops on employability and entrepreneurship.

ROOM 2

- Jordan: In order to select TAIS, the University involved NGOs dealing with psychological problems in refugee camps (permission by Government is needed. Anyway, in Lebanon there are only 7 camps, most of them are living in the community -> easy target to reach).
- Turkey: Target reached through local authorities > Local municipalities contacted them and communicate information about refugees in their district. The issue of TRUST has been raised: Between NGOs / University / Government.
- Spain: Problems in recruitment of participants by NGOs, overprotective. Mistrust towards the university. Key stakeholder, only one NGO really assisted in selecting the participants together with the university.
- Finland: recruited through RED CROSS ASSISTANT in a reception centre. Target: Families, parents, children. Until now only communication.
- Italy: CESIE Network (other organization working in city reception centres, women’s association). Mixed groups of women, from different countries, and different centres. Meetings with them directly in the facilities. Training online too difficult > 2 recruitment and trainings directly in the reception centres.

ROOM 3

- Also, Turkey highlighted mistrust, this time between Government and NGOs, which paralyzed all the situation
TRUST IS THE KEY WORD WORKING WITH REFUGEES.
- Jordan: Government ostracized NGOs until Arab Spring, now they supervise their work. No difficulties in target recruiting, working in area full of VG. Main focus on women. At the beginning, NGOs refused to collaborate with the University, did not want to share data. Afterwards, they discussed together the training material.
- Hungary: The relationship between Government and NGOs depends on the NGO, but of course no welcoming environment.
- Turkey: Some NGOs close- tied with Government, some others not.
- In Italy: In this case no collaboration problems between NGOs and University (not common, as there is a common idea that NGOs do not deliver a serious job, not honest).

ROOM 4

- Italy: Initially managers of the reception centre tested them (face to face meetings showing protocols, activities etc.).
Afterwards, they gained the trust between CESIE and reception centres, which are open for further collaborations, positive feedbacks.
- Jordan: The collaboration with different public sectors (health, politicians) help to get them more practical and get to the refugees' points; they are also preparing materials based on the real needs of refugees. Good relationship with stakeholders all around thanks to the help of the public sector.
- Spain: Before Covid-19, meetings face to face among NGOs/academic/refugees/business people/policy makers, focusing on primary needs. Mistrust towards NGOs, difficulties to access to these people (TAIS participants). Some of them not transparent. Anyway, eventually the dynamic was good: 17 members from NGOs, involved with TAIS evaluation, come participate in the training. Not mistrust, but protectionism.

Why

WHY	<p>Why did you decide for that specific TAIS? (needs, relevance, criteria, assessment methods and practices).</p> <p>NEEDS: Which are the most relevant contextual features making some FDP groups more vulnerable than others in your location?</p> <p>PROCESS: In your TAIS, what should be the mechanism that alleviates the vulnerabilities of these groups?</p> <p>OUTCOME: What do you expect from the TAIS in your country? What kind of results should there be?</p>
<i>Moderator</i>	<i>UH University of Helsinki</i>

Minutes, breakout room “Why”

ROOM 1

“Which are the most relevant contextual features making some FDP groups more vulnerable than others in your location?”

- From Finland, improving child care services in centres and matching young male asylum seekers with young male Finnish men.
- From Spain, a methodology like this means that whatever we are delivering is exactly what the beneficiaries need/want. It is important to customise the aid to the needs of the group and avoid generalisations of vulnerable peoples.
- From Italy, found similar experiences to those of Spain, honing in on the need for creating individualised learning paths for women.
- Lebanon, certain support and care are not always provided for VG. There is an emphasis on basic needs such as healthcare and education, however other needs such as emotional or specialised care are not emphasised.
- Jordan, there is a need for emphasis on psychological development.
- From Turkey, the biggest problem is the increasing population and thus women are constantly becoming more and more vulnerable. In the case that larger governmental organisations cannot always give aid and so the TAIS is to build educational support for the women and their relations with local government support.

ROOM 2

In your TAIS, what should be the mechanism that alleviates the vulnerabilities of these groups?

- Finland, parents would hope for a very inclusive educative progress in which children would have a lot of pressure alleviated from them. It is one of the trickiest questions to discuss as there is a lack of support mechanisms in place.
- From research taken from NGOs in Jordan, there is a clear need for more emotive training within support systems.

- Many from the group agree there is a need for training of support networks that is tailored to the group but that those working with vulnerable groups should be focusing on empathy and recognising the trauma that these VG have experienced as the work is about them and not those aiding them.
- Sum: There was a discussion of the more macro structural levels and the micro personal societal level.

ROOM 3

Which are the most relevant contextual features making some FDP groups more vulnerable than others in your location?

- Finland gave further information about the online forum they have created between young male asylum seekers and Finnish young men.
- Both Spain and Italy had similar experiences of specialising the needs of migrant women particularly due to the high levels of unemployment in both countries.
- The concept of empowerment through specialised support.

ROOM 4

What do you expect from the TAIS in your country? What kind of results should there be?

- The primary and secondary ideas. The project is creating an example of a pilot scheme for municipal governments to learn from. It could also be an inspiration for other NGOs and research groups to create new policies and projects.
- An issue is the sustainability of the project. The EU funding ends and then how will they continue working on the TAIS they had set.
- One of the biggest issues is trying to maintain a pilot scheme such as this that in Turkey and Finland for example, it is quite an outlier to the existing system.

Conclusions

- The groups related to the NEEDS question agreed widely on a need for a methodology that adapts to whatever exactly it is that the beneficiaries need/want. It is important to customise the aid to the needs of the group and avoid generalisations of vulnerable peoples.
- From Jordan there is an emphasis on basic needs such as healthcare and education, however other needs such as emotional or specialised care are not emphasised. Thus, there is a need for specific specialised psychological support in tandem with the projects so as to recognise the trauma that many VG have experienced.
- Through specialised NEEDS, there was a resounding agreement that the more tailored the information, the more we could build on empowerment.
- In relation to PROCESS, what should be the mechanism that alleviates the vulnerabilities of these groups?
- Many from the group agree there is a need for training of support networks that is tailored to the group, but that those working with vulnerable groups should be focusing on empathy and recognising the trauma that these

VG have experienced as the work is about them and not those aiding them, this should be on a macro and micro level.

- In terms of OUTCOMES, the issue raised was mainly sustainability of the pilot regime following the termination of funding. In Turkey and Finland for example, the project is an outlier in some respects to the usual projects in the system. However, in sustaining this project, a serious outcome could be that the project is a good example for municipal governments to implement similar projects and as an inspiration for NGOs and research groups to create policies based of the results of the pilot.
- Engage with the Refugees while also engaging with the professionals who are implementing the strategies.

What

WHAT	<p>What does the TAIS offer? (what type of new, innovative and responsive activities/service is provided)</p> <p>What makes these new/innovative/responsible? What is their operational context?</p> <p>To what extent are these adaptable/transferable to other countries/systems/target populations?</p>
<i>Moderator</i>	<i>Menedék – Hungarian Association for Migrants</i>

Minutes, breakout room “What”

What is your TAIS about?

- (Turkey): Significant amount of vulnerable people (mostly forcibly displaced women and girls from Syrah and northern Iraq) > enabling them to access services and participate in local community, overcome prejudice > concern from local government level regarding the vulnerability of females, because they cannot access health and educational services (participation in civic life in general is limited) > How can they benefit from their rights? Local public authorities were not aware of intercultural/diversity-related issues and hence did not tailor their actions to these needs > they will create a monitoring tool for service providers to improve the quality of their services (training them in advocacy actions, interculturality, diversity etc.).
- (Lebanon): Finding solutions for vulnerable groups (sources of income, access to health care etc.) > TAIS helps to diagnose/identify in which areas they are struggling and what their needs are, after you can take action, evaluate based on feedbacks and results and restart the cycle; it underlines the relation of TAIS to the sustainable development goals .
- (Lebanon): Aiming at locating information > developing small search engine (similar to Google), in which you can find tailored information, AI is narrowing down the vast results to have more results tailored to the needs of vulnerable groups, to be adapted as a smartphone app.
- (Jordan): How to promote the psychosocial support to refugees > through overall empowerment of refugees, 5 sectors: psychosocial, legal, ... empowerment - Action Research Unit to decrease the gap between research and real-life circumstances of these vulnerable groups; creating a platform to sustain the outcomes of this project after the lifetime is over to address their problems online, through a psycho-support website helping them to access information on mental health.
- (Italy): There is a need to empower forcibly displaced women to increase their self-awareness, knowledge on Italian society, autonomy. Topics: Health, Labour, Rights & Duties etc. > bridging what has been developed in RAISD and how to adapt these materials to the real needs of our local migrant women > development of DASI training menu, wide range of educational offers; challenges: mental and physical wellbeing of women living in reception centres in Sicily.
- (Spain): Focusing on women from sub-Saharan countries, many victims of traffic or sexual violence living under the poverty line; TAIS is aiming to increase their employability and social integration.

www.raisd-h2020.eu

Del.7.2 Cross-pilot workshop Report [03/2021]

Coordinator contact: Dr. Rubén Fuentes-Fernández | Universidad Complutense de Madrid | Calle del Profesor José García Santesmases, 9. Ciudad Universitaria 28040 MADRID, Spain.
t: +34/ 91 394 7548 | e: rfuentes@ucm.es | w: www.ucm.es , grasia.fdi.ucm.es

- (Hungary): Enabling social workers to work with vulnerable groups and migrants, context: hostile political environment in Hungary, mostly NGOs provide these services; working with service providers to harmonise service offers in terms of methods and techniques, as well as foster their competences to be able to work in such a complex environment (which they often lack), because services are right now very fragmented > stimulating reflections on their own experiences: How to be more responsible in terms of their own work and in the collaboration with other service providers; developing profiles for “typical” vulnerable groups in Hungary, such as the Middle Eastern gay profile, the single mother profile etc. in order.
- (Jordan): TAIS aimed to empower vulnerable groups and groups in danger of exclusion in several areas to help them interact with the local communities to become more autonomous; hoping to create a standard format so that all NGOs etc. work in a coordinated way, especially in the field of psychological support to provide it whether they are funded or not > building a platform, information gathering space in which there are information on migrants and refugees and inside the social workers, trainers and psychologists can connect with the stakeholders > streamlining and harmonising services; reallocation of resources, because they are not effectively distributed.
- (Finland): Multilingual online discussion groups for young men - locals and migrants promoting learning of both groups and practical information on education and employment opportunities, fostering knowledge on diversity of Finnish participants; improving child care services in reception centres based on needs (researched in interviews) and then offering tailored services fostering well-being of both parents and children.

Adaptability/ sustainability? What is innovative in that?

- (Turkey): An innovative outcome is the monitoring tool.
- (Italy): The approach per se is innovative as it is a selective approach which is already asking: What do YOU need? freedom to choose, empowerment.
- (Italy): DASI is sustainable in terms of transferability to other vulnerable groups.
- (Spain): Agrees with Giovanni, tailored strategies per se are innovative, specificity and also listening > changing the way that we act.
- (Jordan): Working with the Psychological department of YU with the students allowing them to provide these services under supervision of their professors / supervisors; continuous adaptation of TAIS based on actual circumstances.
- (Hungary): Instead of teaching social workers how to work with migrants, they are enabled to make their own observations and reflect on what these stakeholders need; decentralised targeting key actors.
- (Turkey): Web platform on the university homepage making training material available for migrant learners, with info for NGOs and local public authorities to be able to find all the information and support; can depend on themselves.
- (Finland): Building the child care services on already existing ones - improving them; creating a model for reception centres in order to help them provide child care services based on real needs.
- (Turkey): The mentoring tool is sustainable.
- (Spain): Having social enterprises coming in and not only NGOs.

- (Jordan): Gathering the huge amount of information on one website is very innovative, also sharing information between different stakeholders; training materials on psychological support are interesting for and transferable to other stakeholders.
- (Turkey): Segregation is a huge problem - people living in “ghettos”.
- (Hungary): Strengthening the connection between public authorities and organisations in Hungary, because of this an effective collaboration has been missing and this toolbox can help; in-depth look into vulnerability profiles is innovative and will be highly useful.

hoW

HOW	hoW did you design and implement the TAIS? (methodology: assumptions, adjustments, sustainability)
<i>Moderator</i>	<i>UCM Universidad Complutense de Madrid</i>

Minutes, breakout room “hoW”

A1 - Process/Methodology

ROOM 1

- Turkey: Interviews with FDP - second phase diversity trainings - they are implementing the methodology quite well. The important aspect is how the partners are working together: the outcome is the most valuable thing and how the target is benefit from the project. Migration rates will grow in the future and the project is really important for VG.
- Jordan: It was really difficult to decide the strategies they needed to implement. It wasn't easy. They focused on psychological support for HVP within the FDP.

ROOM 2

- Turkey: The more we involve FDP, CSOs and stakeholders in the project, the more they want to be involved.
- Spain: Once they decided the Vulnerable Groups they worked hard with the ARU to contact people and decide how to proceed.
- Lebanon: Collecting data and creating the methodology to make sure it fitted with the sample.
- Italy: Contacting centres and all of them were very interested in the methodologies, some concern about the timing (the situation is dramatic and can change drastically and quickly).

ROOM 3

- Lebanon: It was difficult to put everyone on the table online. For academics it was easy, but not for the others. Some gaps between academics and ministers about the issues (economical, financial especially) when dealing with VG.
- Turkey: We started defining the target.
- Hungary: Problems with different stakeholders, for example the government. But some of the local governments are very receptive but they have many other things to do (so they were not coming). VGs were not really aware about the system and services.

ROOM 4

- Spain: The framework and method of intervention was well introduced. The implementation was easy and gives you the chance to do something really valuable.

- Italy: The designing part was very participatory; it was enriching because of the participation of different professionals.
- Jordan: Firstly, it was difficult because people from the ARUs were from different organisations, now it is easier.
- Finland: The decisional process was tough and we needed to ask for new professionals to be included because of the target.

A2 - Gender Equity aspects

- Jordan: They were taking it into consideration, especially the fact that in Jordan women are considered HV.
- Italy: It was not a matter of gender equality but about people in need. One of the most important VG was first arriving migrants, especially women. They decided to make women interact with women trainers.
- Italy: Working mainly with women, especially with the ones that want to find a job and their place in the hosting country.
- Spain: They try to avoid the gender bias.
- Jordan: The ARU is really balanced.
- Turkey: Adjusting for their VC. ARU members underlined VC about women that were decided to be the target. They all agreed
- Turkey: 60,70% female participation to TAIS and ARU. ARU balanced in terms of gender.

A3 - Ethical issues

- Italy - Flexibility with the group is important
- Hungary: Listening to the FDP you are working with.
- Turkey: sensible issue-> they worked with women early married (11-12 years).

A4 - Participation in the decision

- Hungary: Workshops and meetings to decide the activities.
- Turkey: Very democratic.
- Italy: The process was really participatory, from the one involved in the Competence Cell to the other.
- Italy, Lebanon, Turkey, Jordan and Hungary agreed on the fact that the participation is really democratic.
- Jordan: The coordination gave inputs and a great introduction to the actions.
- Spain: It is being democratic and inclusive.

A5 - ARU working

- Jordan, Turkey and Italy felt very well with the ARU members.
- Lebanon: A bit difficult to create the ARU because stakeholders involved want something in exchange.
- Turkey: Different variety of ARU meetings (participants), also due to Covid-19 restrictions.
- Jordan: Suggesting and preparing training programs and materials together.
- Hungary: Everything transferred online because of the coronavirus.
- Lebanon: Political issues may affect ARU meetings.

A6 - TAIS flexibility

- Italy, Jordan, Hungary they all agree on the flexibility of the TAIS.
- Italy: Be flexible with changing condition.
- Lebanon: Some issues in terms of having reliable data to work on.
- Turkey: They adapted the meeting to go online due to Covid-19 restrictions.
- Jordan: They had the chance to think about the sustainability of the TAIS due to coronavirus.
- Jordan: After any training or meeting they evaluated and exchange the improvement with the participants.
- Italy: Tailored to the need of beneficiaries.
- Spain: They had different meetings to adapt the original plan to the need of the target.
- Finland: Really flexible in terms of asking for the support of other professionals.

A7 - Outcomes and sustainability

- Jordan: They are creating a website to facilitate the data sharing between researchers, NGOs and institutions.
- Lebanon: Find solutions to improve the educational services in Lebanon and reduce poverty. We need to change the culture to create findings useful for the future.
- Italy: the training material could be useful for other target groups with some adjustment.
- Jordan: Re-adaptation of the methods and findings will be useful for future studies.
- Hungary: Trainings and sharing of knowledge after the project, with other organisations.
- Lebanon: They created a survey to analyse the impact after the trainings.

A8 - Recommendations

- Jordan: Exchanging data, training materials and adapt it to the context to let VP be helped and supported.
- Turkey: Be focused on who benefit from the project.
- Lebanon: Change the culture in order to focus on the VG.
- Jordan: Sharing the experience with other stakeholders especially NGOs.
- Lebanon: Take in account new forms of vulnerabilities.
- Finland: To extend the work and create policies.
- Spain: Start involving people who need these services in the decision making.
- Turkey: Improve dissemination.
- Italy: Involve VG in decision making about services.
- Jordan: Sharing data between institutions, NGOs and academics.

raisd

Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced

www.raisd-h2020.eu

Task 7.2 Cross-pilot workshop (n.3)

- 20/01/2022 -

www.raisd-h2020.eu

Del.7.2 Cross-pilot workshop Report [03/2021]

Coordinator contact: Dr. Rubén Fuentes-Fernández | Universidad Complutense de Madrid | Calle del Profesor José García Santesmases, 9. Ciudad Universitaria 28040 MADRID, Spain.
t: +34/ 91 394 7548 | e: rfuentes@ucm.es | w: www.ucm.es , grasia.fdi.ucm.es

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822688.

TASK 7.2 Cross-pilot exchange workshop 3

The third Cross-Analysis workshop's discussion groups evolved around:

- **Retrospective feedback** “Mad, Sad, Glad”: what did most motivate, disappoint and move you?
- **Feed-forward responsiveness** “Better, Stronger, Wiser”: what would you do differently if you had the chance to redo some, or many, parts of your tailored inclusion strategy?

Date and time	Thursday 20/01/2022, 09h30 to 12h30 [CET time].
Agenda	09h30: Welcome 09h45: Retrospective feedback Mad 10h15: Retrospective feedback Sad 10h45: Retrospective feedback Glad >>> 11h15 Break 11h30: Feed-forward responsiveness “ Better, Stronger, Wiser ” 12h00: Sharing experiences 12h30: Acknowledgements and closure
Participants	All partner countries were represented with total 26 participants (22 among ARU and AB members, plus 4 moderators. Gender balance: female 70%, male 30%).
Feedback form	https://forms.gle/63h7UDqZERXkUc6k6
Registration	https://us06web.zoom.us/meeting/register/tZUsd-CpqzIpEtzk4mKVTOBRJ8mXrJ3i9NDR
Dissemination	https://www.facebook.com/raisd.h2020/photos/a.2637854989636072/4704941736260710
<i>Moderators</i>	
CESIE	Plenary Room
UCM Madrid	SAD retrospective frames
Helsinki Univ.	GLAD retrospective frames
Menedék	MAD retrospective frames

The results of this sessions are presented in the tables below.

Retrospective Feed-back

- what did most motivate, disappoint and move you? -

SAD	MAD	GLAD
COVID 19, time to implement as a researcher it takes longer the expected	Budget -- TAIS implementation went in iterative process and each country has it is own situation that means what works in Spain is not working in Jordan.	Helping others, result of the implementation.
Pandemic, unrest in Lebanon and some sample population leaving the program.	Falling behind the original plan of RAISD due to political unrest in Lebanon.	The impact of the Health 4 SEED modules that left huge empowerment on the sample population we worked with. Looking forward to the reliability results of the survey.
It was sad that our trainees were 80 % women and they weren't very aware of the problems both themselves and refugee women/girls have based on gender.	To see people being very prejudiced about refugees in social service field of work made me really mad. I felt (a strong need of) that social workers who work with vulnerable refugees (esp. women and girls) need to learn more about advocacy, gender-based knowledge, diversity and inclusion concepts.	There were no examples of any implementation of training or what so ever in municipality level of social working. They were glad to meet these sets of trainings. Both the municipality we worked with and other two in Eskişehir want to adapt the training program in their work planning. It was good to see our TAIS managed to build something sustainable.
The actual change you can make for vulnerable women. Working with them makes your own privileged position very clear and in the end, after the course you leave and what do you leave them with? Could we really make a difference? I am afraid that we could not do much more than giving them some nice moments, moments where we listened and gave new input, but the system is too closed and difficult to make a longer impact.	Covid-19 lockdowns that obliged us to do activities online with vulnerable women who had no digital competences. No good follow-up plan for the participants. Although the final product of the menu is great and good for sustainability, there were no real follow up plans for the participants of the training.	Comprehensive tool (menu) for future trainings + able to give some happy moments and relation building.
It's actually the same as the MAD.	That we couldn't keep the resources and keep providing child care activities as much after the TAIS pilot implementation. It almost went back to	That we had more resources to give more childcare activities to the children in the reception centre.

SAD	MAD	GLAD
	how it was before the TAIS pilot implementation.	
Sad that the COVID did not allow really to see if the TAIS could work as it was nearly impossible to become an entrepreneur during this period.	The low amount of time and budget spent on the implementation of the TAIS compared with the whole process of meetings, assessment and evaluation, etc.	Glad of all the actors that I have met during all the RAISD project. It has really helped me networking. I have used some of these contacts of the people I met in the ARUs to improve my everyday work in Mundo en Movimiento.
Demotivation of people because of the many crisis attacking Lebanon.	Pandemic and Financial crisis that prevented us from having face to face training and some students were unable to join online training because of electricity and internet problems. Also, field visits to camps were cancelled.	The feedback of the students regarding the skills they acquired during the workshops organized by the LIU Health Committee.
Especially as regards training courses, apparently the composition of the classrooms was not always the same: some participants did not attend all the sessions, and this reduces the effectiveness of the training. Also, in one case, social workers working with migrants had a negative approach to VGs.	We did not implement a TAIS, the most difficult part was to understand the expected contents of D6.2, D6.3 and D7.1 and to avoid duplications with other deliverables.	Collection of lessons learnt, knowing the mistakes not to be repeated.
In our local settings, it was not realistic (from a TAIS perspective) to target directly vulnerable refugees at a micro-level and also, it was hopeless to indicate changes in the (macro) policy level.	When I realized that there is no budget to pay some professionals to comment on our handbook for service providers.	The good feedback we have received from professionals from different fields after reading the 1.0 version of our toolbox material.
The fact that the realities of the Syrian refugees are extremely dire and that a lot of them carry sentiments of hopelessness.	The economic situation and Covid-19 meant that things were not going as smoothly as possible.	The potential to cater to vulnerable communities and to make a chance on both social and educational levels.

SAD	MAD	GLAD
Learning about the difficult situation and life context of PFD and becoming truly aware of their challenges locally and globally. Our difficulty of engaging and creating constancy among some of the participants, in spite of our efforts (lack of real interaction due to online activities). The feeling of not always fulfilling the expectations.	The budget was not adjusted to the TAIS needs and not being able to fully adapt the training to the different knowledge levels of participants.	The improvements and progress of the TAIS participants, little pieces of positive news about them. The contributions and collaboration of our ARU members.
Cheap labour.	Vulnerability of refugees.	Refugee Women are getting stronger.
It has been observed that the Turks have lost their sense of pity towards the VGs due to the prejudices and the bad economic situation in Turkey. Especially because of the Syrian refugees, there is a lot of hate speech, discrimination and marginalization. In addition, service providers are very attached to patriarchal ideas about gender, women's and children's rights and they do not want to abandon these ideas.	The prejudices which are about VG of the service providers and their strict adherence to these prejudices were the most challenging factors for us in TAIS implementation. Those who think that the government especially treats Syrian refugees with privilege, have not lost their prejudices despite the training provided.	The service provider, most of whom are university graduates, stated that they had never taken a course on gender, women's rights, access to rights, and multiculturalism. Service providers said that thanks to TAIS trainings, they have become more aware of gender, women's rights, access to rights, cultural diversity and multiculturalism, and they want to learn more about these issues. They also agreed that these issues should be promoted in society.

Feed-forward Recommendations

“Better, Stronger, Wiser”

What would you do differently if you had the chance to redo some, or many, parts of your tailored inclusion strategy?

- Budget reallocation, time to implement.
- More emphasis on Education Psychology and engaging more Syrian NGOs rather than Lebanese ones. We can now widen the education landscape and cater to the contemporary vulnerabilities to be more precise.
- More follow up possibilities for the actual beneficiaries that could have a long-term impact or ensure other kind of collaborations that could provide this kind of follow-up.
- To also think about how the implementation could continue after the project.
- I think some small formal or informal communication specially while implementing the TAIS. Maybe a newsletter, but not the general RAISD one, telling how it was going could have provided more involvement and more thoughtful opinions in the ARUs.
- Something that worked for me to have a strong commitment with the project, as an ARU member, was having the opportunity to have some informal, not only related to RAISD, contact with different RAISD members from the UCM. Maybe having more stable members of the ARU could be better for the discussion.
- More detailed needs analysis. Work with NGOs as they are very active in the Refugees sector.
- A different budget design would provide a more place for effective TAIS implementation. The expectation of working with volunteers to such an extent was too high and reduced flexibility.
- Make sure that content takes into the vulnerable background of the students. This can be remedied through professional development.
- Have different levels of training to participants of different package of knowledge. Tailoring the TAIS to the even more specific needs of migrants, offering training on vulnerably persons and FDP to program service providers.
- Different city different refugees.
- I increased the number of TAIS trainings. I would also expand the variety of topics included in the trainings. If possible, I would have these trainings spread throughout the country.

Conclusions

The organisation of the Cross-pilot Exchange Workshops contributed in setting up the RAISD 'H2020 Knowledge Community', providing support to all actors involved in the TAIS processes to be responsible, ensuring that RRI becomes — and remains — a solid and continuous reality, ultimately seeking to further improve methodological aspects within and around the local attention and inclusion strategies (TAIS) for Highly Vulnerable Groups affected by forced displacement.

Considering the diversity of the TAISes in concept, design and expected results, the three Multi-stakeholder Workshops focused on different methodological and quality assessing TAIS aspects after each piloting round. Each Workshop provided opportunity for thematic- rooms to discuss country specific problems inherent in each TAIS (not contextual factors) and find some commonalities between different contexts.

The **first exchange-workshop** was attended by 33 participants [28 among Action Research Unit (ARU) and Advisory Board (AB) members, plus 5 moderators. Gender balance: female 56%, male 44%] and aimed to provide a critical perspective on how the first piloting round was designed and implemented (including e.g. barriers and enablers) and also to generate some initiatives on how to further improve project aspects over the duration of the project. The discussion groups evolved around an initial SWOT Analysis and related relevant questions (see [Annex 1](#)):

- **Strengths** [internal]: What do you do well? What unique resources can you draw on?
- **Weaknesses**: What could you improve? Where do you have fewer resources than others?
- **Opportunities** [external]: What good opportunities are open to you and your VG? What trend/policies (internal and external to your institution) could you take advantage of? How can you turn your strengths into opportunities?
- **Threats** [external]: What trends/policies (internal and external to your institution) could hinder your TAIS success? What threats do your weaknesses exposes you?

The **second exchange-workshop** was attended by 51 participants [42 among ARU and AB members, plus 5 moderators, 4 minute-takers. Gender balance: female 60%, male 40%] and aimed at gathering constructive critical viewpoints on TAIS developments after the second piloting round, allowing to further improve methodological aspects within and around the local attention and inclusion strategies for Highly Vulnerable Groups. The discussion groups evolved around the "4W Questions":

- **Who** is part of the TAIS? (involvement HVG and ARU; TAIS collaborations: Stakeholders and Networks).
- **Why** did you decide for that specific TAIS? (needs, relevance, criteria, assessment methods and practices).
- **What** does the TAIS offer? (what type of new, innovative and responsive activities/service is provided).
- **hoW** did you design and implement the TAIS? (methodology: assumptions, adjustments, sustainability).

The **third exchange-workshop** was attended by 26 participants [22 among ARU and AB members, plus 4 moderators. Gender balance: female 70%, male 30%] and aimed at gathering critical viewpoints on the implemented TAIS in the different partner countries. The discussion groups evolved around:

- **Retrospective feedback** "Mad, Sad, Glad": what did most motivate, disappoint and move you?

- **Feed-forward responsiveness** “Better, Stronger, Wiser”: what would you do differently if you had the chance to redo some, or many, parts of your tailored inclusion strategy?

To conclude, the TAISs as processes were evaluated by studying how accessible it is, to what extent people use it, what kind of resources it provides for different stakeholders and how easy it is to set up. Further, evaluating the TAISs as outcomes pushes one to look for changes in the level of capabilities and competences of the involved stakeholders, who through the workshops revealed barriers and enablers at all three Socio-ecological Model's level (micro-meso-macro).

The [RAISD Observatory](#) will continue benefitting from the RAISD Knowledge Community to pursue its mission and vision:

MISSION: To provide a comprehensive and collaborative forum for interchanging ideas and knowledge between professionals and organizations working in forced migration, putting the needs, challenges and experiences of displaced people at the very core of the initiative. To enhance the value of civil society organizations' work and making their initiatives, projects and programs visible. Furthermore, it aims to facilitate access to basic information for refugees and asylum seekers.

VISION: Contribute to making forcibly displaced people, their needs, challenges and opportunities more visible to the society, and drawing specific attention to the most vulnerable persons among the displaced. To become a lively reference community for the variety of stakeholders working within forced migration that contributes to co-creating initiatives that can improve the life conditions and empower forcibly displaced people.

Acknowledgements

Hereby we would like thank all Action-Research Units and Advisory Board's members contributing to the success of the Cross-Analysis piloting Workshops by sharing and building upon specific knowledge and implementation experiences.

raisd

Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced

www.raisd-h2020.eu

- Annex 1 -

SWOT Analysis

Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats

www.raisd-h2020.eu

Del.7.2 Cross-pilot workshop Report [03/2021]

Coordinator contact: Dr. Rubén Fuentes-Fernández | Universidad Complutense de Madrid | Calle del Profesor José García Santesmases, 9. Ciudad Universitaria 28040 MADRID, Spain.
t: +34/ 91 394 7548 | e: rfuentes@ucm.es | w: www.ucm.es , grasia.fdi.ucm.es

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822688.

SWOT Analyses by local Action-Research Units

- Workshop 1/December 2020 -

SWOT your TAIS	
[Internal] STRENGTHS	[Internal] WEAKNESSES
<p><i>What do you do well? What unique resources can you draw on?</i></p> <p><u>EXAMPLES:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advantages of TAIS co-created design Value, quality of strategy Resources, Assets, People Innovative aspects Experience, knowledge, data Processes, systems, communications Self-help and peer support Monitoring and improvement of work methodologies Procedural improvement (new or different services, methodologies) Improved accessibility (information, opening hours, location, language) 	<p><i>What could you improve? Where do you have fewer resources than others?</i></p> <p><u>EXAMPLES:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Disadvantages of TAIS co-created design Gaps in capabilities Reputation, presence and reach Financial issues Timescale, deadlines and pressure Location and geographical outreach Effects on core activities, distractions Plan predictability Morale, commitment, leadership Processes and system Management cover, succession
[External] OPPORTUNITIES	[External] THREATS
<p><i>What good opportunities are open to you and your VG? What trend/policies (internal & external to your institution) could you take advantage of? How can you turn your strengths into opportunities?</i></p> <p><u>EXAMPLES:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research development and innovation Helix Stakeholder cooperation collaboration Networking and influences Changes in skills / attitude / knowledge of staff Material changes Procedural improvement 	<p><i>What trends/policies (internal & external to your institution) could hinder your TAIS success? What threats do your weaknesses exposes you?</i></p> <p><u>EXAMPLES:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Political effects Legislative effects Sustaining internal capabilities obstacles faced Insurmountable weaknesses Loss of key staff Sustainable financial backing

Spain

TAIS: Refuge of power | Sub-Saharan women's entrepreneurship and coaching program

UCM - Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain

STRENGTHS [internal, positive]

· *Advantages of TAIS co-created design*

Tailored activity. The design and implementation followed the criteria of a tailored attention and inclusion activity designed to respond to the specific needs of one of the vulnerable groups (detected in the Action Research Unit (ARU) and in interviews with potential beneficiaries).

Stakeholders increase in number and nature. Stakeholders have been increased in number and nature (accordingly to the quintuple helix). The design of the TAIS has made it possible to identify new potential stakeholders, particularly business-related ones (which were difficult to engage since the beginning of RAISD). Through TAIS they are engaged in RAISD activities and its future Observatory. Besides, TAIS has allowed several stakeholders to get involved in its' implementation.

Strong and solid participation processes. In general terms, ARU members from the diverse helix groups have participated in a very active way in the co-design and evaluation of our TAIS, with around 20 participants in all the workshops we have organized up to the moment.

Tools have been designed and implemented to allow stakeholders contribution in different ways: at the 5th (in presence) ARU meeting -25th February 2020-; at the two online ARU meetings 12th May 2020 and July 2020; via the online survey July 2020. Besides, a summary and update documents have been provided to ARU members and interested stakeholders in order to keep them informed and to engage them in the process. Thus, stakeholders have had formal channels to participate and they have made valuable contributions to the TAIS's design. In this sense, numbers speak for themselves: 18 ARU members at the aforementioned 5th meeting, 23 ARU members at the 6th ARU meeting, one online survey addressed to entities, more than 20 ARU members at the 7th ARU meeting on the 26th of June 2020 and the 8th ARU meeting on the 4th of November 2020. Stakeholders have also taken active part in the first round evaluation: 15 ARU members attended the 8th ARU meeting on the 4th of November 2020. Furthermore, an Evaluation Workshop was organized (on the 2nd of December 2020) to gather feedback on the TAIS. In addition, teachers answered to a tailored questionnaire (-2 responses from 4 external teachers).

· *Value, quality of strategy*

(see previous point)

Preliminary criteria guide monitoring and evaluation. TAIS has followed the RAISD SMART criteria that have guided the design and implementation (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-based -realistic / feasible; and Sustainable).

Information has reached key stakeholders. Two customised brochures were designed: a custom one for entities (stakeholders) and another for potential beneficiaries.

TAIS: Refuge of power | Sub-Saharan women's entrepreneurship and coaching program

Flexibility and adaptation. RAISD and TAIS unique methodology (strongly supported by RRI) allows changes as a natural dynamic. Among them, changes that respond to beneficiaries' demands.

Recognition. Beneficiaries consider their opinion as important and relevant within TAIS and RAISD.

- *Resources, Assets, People*

Quality and suitable. Resources are perceived appropriate and of value.

Excellence. Training is developed by highly experienced specialists in the subjects (entrepreneurship and micro-business developers; women empowerment experts; UCM lecturers; experts on discrimination and diversity).

Complementary support. Extra support has been available from the start to the beneficiaries (to cover potential dropouts and other difficulties): free Spanish lessons; a tablet per participant with prepaid internet connection been distributed to the participants before starting the training.

- *Innovative aspects*

Participation (see above) & **RRI** perspective are core principles of functioning.

Covid19's adaptation and Online training. The situation derived from the confinement, lockdowns, and the measures due to Covid19, has resulted in a transformation of the last phase of the TAIS design. It represents a continuous challenge that is solved in a positive way, since the initial objectives have been maintained. Technological adaptations have been produced, materials have been simplified, and accompaniment has been provided to the participants.

One-to-one follow-up and tailored evaluation system. The monitoring methodology implies the complementary action of several actors. The monitoring involves the members of the ARU. It has a technical and micro dimension through the UCM team with respect to the weekly development of the TAIS (with other stakeholders engaged in its implementation). Finally, it has a human dimension, also weekly. This means there is a reference person to accompany all the beneficiaries, in addition to the WhatsApp messages, mails and telephone calls, as well as the twice per week sessions. Besides, there is the formal evaluation process at the end of each experimental round.

- *Experience, knowledge, data*

Strong Leadership. UCM leadership and identification of key stakeholders with leadership and commitment in the process (Nantik Lum & PAZ AI). UCM previous work experience, projects and previous activities with some members of the ARU.

- *Processes, systems, communications*

Needs, expectations and strengths were identified since the beginning.

High adaptability. The demands of the participants have been heard quickly, depending on when they have been expressed. In September the training program was modified; the current version is the 9th one.

- *Self-help and peer support*

TAIS: Refuge of power | Sub-Saharan women's entrepreneurship and coaching program

Beneficiaries perceive themselves as complementary. The knowledge of the group, and group cohesion, have been a specific objective complementary to the training. It has resulted in the recognition of each of the women as valuable and different components that contribute different aspects to the team.

- *Monitoring and improvement of work methodologies*
(see above)

Participation (see above) & RRI perspective are core principles of functioning.

Covid19's adaptation and Online training.

One-to-one follow-up and tailored evaluation system.

Weekly personal monitoring. Content and time progression have been evaluated weekly with trainers by mail and phone, WhatsApp, and a daily available social worker for one to one flow-up (see above).

- *Procedural improvement (new or different services, methodologies)*

Participatory approach. On the top of the participatory topics already pointed out, all teachers applied a participatory approach. In all sessions, there has been debate among the participants with different points of view, allowing some to solve the doubts raised by others.

Gender mainstreaming. The gender perspective has been applied in the selection of trainers, content, time and duration and educative strategy. This dimension is considered in the weekly monitoring process.

- *Improved accessibility (information, opening hours, location, language)*

Accessibility is guaranteed. One of the advantages of online training is that it respects the pace of each person, and their availability, within a pre-established time frame. The chosen schedule is the one that favours the greatest attendance (days and hours). The online format has allowed the TAIS to be carried out in spite of the pandemic. Free Spanish classes have been offered since the beginning of the TAIS through a specialized entity for training in the Spanish language for online migrants (Speak Madrid). The format and methodology of the training has undergone a great adaptation by the teachers (dynamics, sessions and learning rhythm).

- *Goals and achievements completed*

The **expected results have been fulfilled:**

- The participants have improved their knowledge and capabilities (technology, social rights, women's rights, personal strengths, labour market, and entrepreneurship).
- Beneficiaries have seen inspiring examples of migrant women entrepreneurs.
- The project has provided them with the necessary material resources to be able to participate in the training (data, tablet, learning materials).
- Participants have got familiarised with the online training format.
- Trust. Users are increasingly proactive when asking questions or proposing ideas, it seems that a space of trust is being created in which they can participate without feeling judged by their colleagues or trainers.
- Teachers are satisfied.

TAIS: Refuge of power | Sub-Saharan women's entrepreneurship and coaching program

- Most of the teachers have adapted to the technical challenge of online training.
- Experts on entrepreneurship and other subjects have improved their knowledge of refugee women and international protection situations/issues.
- Stakeholders consider that the TAIS could be replicated in other learning contexts (after adaptations)
- There has been a transfer of knowledge to stakeholders. There are policy recommendations at the meso level that are being accepted by stakeholders.
- Exchange and networking are getting very active. Stakeholders, including beneficiaries participate in activities of other organisations (e.g. UNHCR December training session).

WEAKNESSES [internal, negative]

· *Disadvantages of TAIS co-created design*

Lack of practical expertise. ARU members -specialized entities on international protection and migration- lacked expertise on entrepreneurship; this affected the first program design of the training content (the experts have joined after the launch of the TAIS, (after finishing Module 0).

Mismatches of needs' perception. The reception and integration process in Spain favours this process. Also, cultural influences on the expression of disagreement may play a role. There have been mismatches between *felt needs* (by beneficiaries) and *perceived needs* (expressed by expert ARU members). The needs indicated by experts in the field of inclusion: fundamental rights, social resources, resources in terms of participation, have not been perceived as relevant by all the participants (because they already had this knowledge). The needs indicated by experts regarding social skills and emotional capacities to undertake, have not been perceived as relevant among some of the participants. For instance, the content on gender: women's rights and violence against women, have not been perceived as so relevant. Different perspectives towards short/long term integration objectives generate mismatches between the urgency of finding a job and the goals related to business and self-employment in a longer term.

Heterogeneity management. There were challenges regarding identification and selection of participants, with regard of their short and long term goals, learning paces, different backgrounds, expectations and needs. The group is co-responsible of decisions and the design is flexible. This flexibility sometimes generates uncertainty about the final goal (eg.: Consensus regarding the final idea of business has been quite difficult to reach as all voices are paid attention to, commitment and personal interest among beneficiaries varies). But in spite of this, a unique business idea has been created.

Length. Time-programming of the content is not developed to the satisfaction of all participants. Some consider that it has been repetitive and too slowly.

Patronizing. Patronizing is perceived as an attitude towards participants with less commitment (punctuality, participation, homework, self-study time). It is a challenge to find out what consequences this might have for the course, and the team, without letting people out of the training. There is not a consensus on the basic rules of participation.

TAIS: Refuge of power | Sub-Saharan women's entrepreneurship and coaching program

· *Gaps in capabilities*

Technology. The weaknesses in the use of technologies among the beneficiaries have been greater than those initially detected. They need more support than expected and it has caused difficulties in being able to access the course content, carry out exercises and interact with classmates and the teaching team.

Gender dimension. The gender issues are already known to some participants. However, they do not know how to link this information to the entrepreneurship training, and how it affects their personal lives and professional development. Personal, religious and cultural beliefs interfere.

Language. The lack of understanding or ability to express oneself in Spanish makes it difficult to interact and understand the training materials.

Beneficiaries' performance efficiency. Time of personal study is not developed as expected. Thus, the hours of training in entrepreneurship (business development models) are perceived as insufficient by teachers. Given the initial (low) level of knowledge of some of the participants there is a lack of personal time of study.

Active participation varies. The personal involvement of the participants is variable. Availability for assistance is affected by different variables. Involvement, active listening and personal focus on the session need to be improved. The online methodology, the heterogeneity of the group and the socio-personal context of vulnerability affect the participation.

Cultural knowledge. Above all about the context of entrepreneurship in Spain and the procedures necessary to start a business. Among the participants there is little knowledge about the sector in which they want to undertake the business (African food products and cosmetics), the identification of potential clients in Spain, the society and the cultural characteristics, about consumer behaviour, competitor behaviour and competitive advantages, etc.

· *Reputation, presence and reach*

No more weaknesses identified at the moment.

· *Financial issues*

Initial costs. The prepaid data of the tablets is sometimes insufficient for the participants (more personal study time or materials' review).

Replicability challenges. Those TAIS collaborators not receiving any financial compensation find it difficult to justify the TAIS sessions within their own programs. This hinders the satisfaction of trainers. It can also affect the replicability of the experience.

· *Timescale, deadlines and pressure*

Single collective result. The purpose of establishing a cooperative was very ambitious and it requires conditions that are not easy to meet. Therefore, in the initial phase different entrepreneurship's results were settled.

Assimilation of information. Information about the timeline and content has not been fully understood by all beneficiaries. The timeframe of expectations of the participants for the implementation of the project is variable.

TAIS: Refuge of power | Sub-Saharan women's entrepreneurship and coaching program

Despite having the information, it has not always been assimilated as such. There were participants who thought that in 6 months the business project would be finished.

Gaps in capabilities greater than expected. The lack of personal study among some beneficiaries (tasks and homework) delays the whole group. It makes the group goes more slowly than expected and it affects the timescales.

No more weaknesses identified at the moment (excluding Covid19).

- *Location and geographical outreach*

Online process makes bonding difficult. The lack of personal exchange (in person) between the trainers and the participants, and between the participants, makes it difficult to bond emotionally with the project.

No more weaknesses have been identified at the moment.

- *Effects on core activities, distractions*

No weaknesses identified at the moment (in addition to Covid19).

- *Plan predictability*

No weaknesses identified at the moment.

- *Morale, commitment, leadership*

Weakness in appropriation. Some participants hope to join an entrepreneurial project already done (closed) and find it difficult to understand that the development of the project depends on their personal attitude, their commitment and their time of dedication.

Initial mismatch of expectations. As already explained, the expectations of some beneficiaries (those with greater knowledge or experience in entrepreneurship) have not been met until the TAIS has focused on the content on "business development". The contents on capacity building, on social inclusion, or on gender issues, were not in their personal objectives. This has implied some demotivation.

Lack of commitment with tasks and punctuality. Among some participants there is little responsibility in carrying out the tasks and homework. Their active attitude towards the course varies. Teachers consider this as a demotivating factor.

Motivation varies. The most motivated beneficiaries perceive that the less committed ones make it difficult to reach their personal entrepreneurship goals. UCM wants to reinforce the value of the group, in order to arrive as a team, give mutual support, etc. but the most motivated beneficiaries have more individualistic goals of their own. On the other hand, all participants prioritise short-term job opportunities. There is a tension between maintaining the entire number of participants and satisfying the most motivated participants.

Depersonalization. The participant's gadget camera is often switched off because they are at work, they don't have privacy, or they don't have a proper place they feel comfortable to show. This is hard to understand for teachers and some colleagues.

TAIS: Refuge of power | Sub-Saharan women's entrepreneurship and coaching program

Bonding ties. Outside the sessions there is not an active contact among all the beneficiaries. For the moment, ties of friendship and mutual support or solidarity are developed in small groups. Attachment among all the participants is still a challenge.

- *Processes and system*

Vulnerabilities are challenges to tailor-made activities. Personal data and information about personal circumstances are difficult to identify. Protection of users' data has prevented some trainers from accessing personal information while others have developed their own strategies to access this information through the beneficiaries. This has caused difficulties to the design and adaptation of the course. It has made the initial assessment of participants problematic to define and teachers have found it challenging to adapt to the specific needs of each person in the group.

Privacy cultures. Some participants do not share the camera in the training sessions, or not during the entire course. It has a demoralising effect as the group cannot bond and literally see each other.

Content appropriation. Some of the content of the program has not always been understood as necessary, especially the generic subjects not directly related to business development (e.g. resources, skills, capacities). Although beneficiaries have finally appreciated this content, it was not seen a priority for the participants.

Communication barriers. There have been communication barriers due to Spanish language level added to internet connection problems for some participants.

Modification of the final product. Expectations and resource allocation were not clear enough as some RAISD stakeholders consider that resources for TAIS might be insufficient to achieve the goal of starting a business. Perhaps it is not understood that it is about creating the key capabilities/ conditions so that beneficiaries feel empowered to do it and materialise it (not to undertake a specific business by RAISD). Initially, there was an investment resource for the implementation of a cooperative entrepreneurship project. However, reallocation funds do not allow this kind of investment. This fact does not modify the objectives of the TAIS, but it does modify the way in which the results can be materialized.

- *Management cover, succession*

Monitoring sequence. The team lacked a profile of social worker who could carry out a social and emotional accompaniment more adapted to the needs of the beneficiaries. A person dedicated to those tasks resigned unexpectedly.

Technology support. The data consumption plan has fallen short for training sessions and study time. Demands on tech support have been greater than expected.

UCM- team horizontal structure. One stakeholder considers that the interlocutors for the different parts of the project are too many. The information exchange structure is not clear.

OPPORTUNITIES [external, positive]

- *Research development and innovation*

TAIS: Refuge of power | Sub-Saharan women's entrepreneurship and coaching program

Open scope. The proposal is attractive for beneficiaries and stakeholders. There are very few specialized offers in entrepreneurship training for migrants; practically none aimed at refugees or asylum seekers, and to a lesser extent women and vulnerable groups.

Promising alternative. Refugees and asylum seekers face high unemployment levels, self-employment represent an attractive and feasible alternative.

- *Helix Stakeholder cooperation collaboration*

Complementarity. The TAIS is an attractive project for specialised organisations which have no previous experience with refugee population and do not reach highly vulnerable groups, which are interested in them.

- *Networking and influences*

Favourable stakeholders. There are specialised and interested stakeholders: entrepreneurship programs towards local population (migrant and not-migrant) are promoted through private non-governmental organisations such as Ashoka or Nantik Lum Foundation (among others), as well as public employment policies and labour organisations (such as The Federation of Associations of Self-Employed Workers (ATA)). Local and regional governments are also interested. There is a regulatory framework for entrepreneurship that also includes promoting policies.

- *Changes in skills / attitude / knowledge of staff*

Potential impacts in stakeholders/Learning opportunities for external organisations . The entities of the ARU and those that participate as stakeholders in the TAIS state that there has been a transfer of knowledge and consider that they can effectively appropriate the criteria and intervention instruments for their organisations . Outside the TAIS and beyond RAISD, the project generates policy recommendations available for external stakeholders.

- *Material changes*

Funding and regulatory framework. The national and regional framework in the country is promoting the positive image of entrepreneurship. There are complementary training and funding opportunities. However, no reference is made to the migrant or refugee population.

- *Procedural improvement*

Synergies. There are stakeholders with complementary activities and approaches in entrepreneurship that favour the exchange and synergies between different events and processes. E.g.: Nantik Lum and UNHCR organize events open to TAIS participants.

THREATS [external, negative]

- *Political effects*

Lack of inclusion policies. The lack of a national inclusion programme for migrants and refugees/asylum seekers affects negatively the policy context.

TAIS: Refuge of power | Sub-Saharan women's entrepreneurship and coaching program

Inclusion policies are unspecific. They don't address the needs of highly vulnerable groups among the forcibly displaced.

Uncertainty of legal status (regarding international protection request for asylum seekers).

Racist anti-immigration discourse. Media discourse and political parties' discourses. Attitudes of the population of little knowledge and prejudices about refugees.

Ethnic niching in segmented labour markets and racial discrimination.

COVID-19 is causing an economic crisis.

- *Legislative effects*

Lack of specific policy. There is not a specific regulation regarding entrepreneurship for asylum seekers or refugees in Spain. Regulation for foreigners who want to set up a business in Spain is related to migration visas, not inclusion policies. The regulatory framework for entrepreneurship in Spain is relatively recent and the legal forms of companies and self-employment are diverse and do not specifically support refugees' initiatives.

Lack of specific funding for entrepreneurs with refugees' background.

Bank bureaucracy. Opening an account and loans' conditions are harder for asylum seekers.

- *Sustaining internal capabilities*

Difficulties inherent to entrepreneurship (for anyone).

COVID-19 related issues.

- *Obstacles faced*

Lack of previous good practices. There are few previous examples to learn from, and experiences to look at, due to the lack of practices aimed at refugees as entrepreneurs, and specifically at women asylum seekers.

Lack of internet access. COVID-19 measures in municipalities have restricted the free internet access points (for example in public libraries). Access to free connexion and data for individual study and in-depth content download are cut down.

Lack of personal interaction due to COVID-19 measures. Not being able to carry out in presence trainings and exchange sessions have weakened the creation of links between the own participants, which is essential if the objective is to undertake a business together.

- *Insurmountable weaknesses*

Unemployment and financial needs. Some of the participants have financial problems due to their personal circumstances. They must prioritize their job search over their participation in the project.

Gender-based cultural norms and barriers.

Changes in legal status. Such as: the abandonment of the request of international protection; departure from Spain; the rejection of international protection; etc.

TAIS: Refuge of power | Sub-Saharan women's entrepreneurship and coaching program

Natural morbidity of the population. Diseases and death.

- *Loss of key staff*

Loss of key staff. The team member responsible for the individualized follow-up had to return to her country of origin and left the project.

- *Sustainable financial backing*

No weakness identified.

Other:

Lack of data and knowledge. The OECD "Policy brief on refugee entrepreneurship" states that "little is known about the exact prevalence, specific barriers and benefits related to entrepreneurship by people with a refugee background, and particularly by those of the recent refugee wave." (OECD, 2019:4).

Developing Actionable Strategies

Considering the above analysis, what will you adjust or do differently in the following TAIS piloting round?

- One-to-one meetings with women and team members have begun to be implemented.
- A face-to-face meeting per month is being planned -within or outside the scope of the UCM- with the beneficiaries, as long as the pandemic restrictions allow it. The group activities will be focused on the development of the business project and also, to create group cohesion (the participants have not shown a keen interest and initiative in organizing friendly gatherings among them).
- Personal photographs should be added on each participant profile to personalize and bond to each other.
- A new team UCM member has been hired with a profile of social worker. She has started to carry out the social and emotional accompaniment of the beneficiaries, adapted to their specific needs.
- A strategy to attract new participants (with pre-training in entrepreneurship) was launched (November-December 2020) to incorporate potential new beneficiaries to the group and optimize the scope of the TAIS, but the profiles of persons interested did not match the TAIS requirements.
- The monitoring system for the fulfilment of weekly exercises and tasks has to be more exhaustive, the team is working on it. It is necessary to innovate in motivation and rules of engagement and permanence.
- Working in subgroups will be analysed, based on the levels of motivation and involvement of the participants, in order to satisfy different expectations of the participants and to improve the mutual support within the project (mentoring services provided). This kind of adjustments to be carried out during TAIS round 2 were contemplated in the initial TAIS-design and shows the responsiveness of the process.
- Next activities regarding gender issues and socio-emotional capabilities should be carefully pre-valued with participants to adjust expectations, contents and their link to the course.
- Inclusion of a parallel training (or reinforcement) in financial education sessions are considered to be added into the training program.
- Strengthen the link of Spanish entrepreneurs with the TAIS, in order to improve the participants' cultural knowledge about Spanish society and markets.

TAIS: Refuge of power | Sub-Saharan women's entrepreneurship and coaching program

- Spanish language learning of the participants will be more closely monitored.
- Technology use and resources will be reinforced as a core content in the TAIS.

Italy

TAIS: Digitalised Personal Pathways

CESIE, Italy

STRENGTHS [internal, positive]

- SELECTIVE approach (Participatory spirit towards the novelty approach proposal and promotion willingness by ARU members).
- Robust and sustainable TAIS software infrastructure (DASI).
- TAIS is offered in accordance with institution capacities:
 - Experienced, ethic and flexible Trainers' Hub.
 - Professional Mentoring: sensitivity for cultural translations and adaptations.
- Multicultural, multilingual and multi-religious group dynamics.
- The practice pursues a policy for orientation, mentoring and tutoring of co-experts/beneficiaries.
- The practice design is based on operational flexibility (from F2F to online streaming training, ultimately recording training sessions).

WEAKNESSES [internal, negative]

- Engagement of the HVG co-experts was quite unpredictable.
- First recruitment model was not profitable in times of social restrictions.
- Need for more and better local information campaigning.
- Low linguistic and digital competences by mentors and participants.
- Mentors/Resource women ("power balance") > HVG' complete confidence in their opinion leaves aside almost completely the autonomous active participation.
- Training migrants requires the establishment of a trainer-trainee relationship based on esteem and trust. Re-entering education requires a strong and regular relation with trainers and mentors > inability to create relationship and team work due to c-19 restrictions for in-presence meetings.
- Need for second recruitment round (responsive strategy against digital-dropouts).
- Participants' limited access to digital devices and wireless internet connections.

OPPORTUNITIES [external, positive]

- Training opportunities (RRI, OER, Gender, evaluation frameworks and criteria)
- Changing HVGs' attitude and behaviour for inclusion (less assistance providing approach, increased level of autonomy).
- The practice facilitates individuals' adjustment with the national integration systems' environment.
- Political impact of council of ministers adopting a decree that reverses many of the worst policies imposed by the previous interior minister and current leader of the anti-immigrant League Party, Matteo Salvini. In early October 2020, the Italian government adopted a new immigration decree that significantly modified two so-called security decrees, issued in 2018 and 2019, by the previous government.

THREATS [external, negative]

www.raisd-h2020.eu

Del.7.2 Cross-pilot workshop Report [03/2021]

Coordinator contact: Dr. Rubén Fuentes-Fernández | Universidad Complutense de Madrid | Calle del Profesor José García Santesmases, 9. Ciudad Universitaria 28040 MADRID, Spain.
t: +34/ 91 394 7548 | e: rfuentes@ucm.es | w: www.ucm.es , grasia.fdi.ucm.es

TAIS: Digitalised Personal Pathways

- Covid-19 outbreaks. Ongoing social interaction restrictions > difficulty in planning suitable and feasible implementation timeframe.
- Stakeholder fatigue caused by too many requests from research projects, often without gain for the stakeholders.
- HVG's mistrust in authorities and host community.
- HVG's constructed identities can often be difficult to reconcile with those of learners or students.
- Lack of participants' motivation, strongly connected to:
 - Their uncertain status: some migrants simply wait for the documents to continue the journey to other countries. However, in some cases, it takes more than two years to go through the legal process.
 - the huge impact of those narratives according to which is not necessary to learn the local language in order to find a low-skilled job.
- Persisting downward labour inclusion and segregation in the low-wage, unprotected sectors of the labour market.

Developing Actionable Strategies

Considering the above analysis, what will you adjust or do differently in the following TAIS piloting round?

Responsive change in recruitment model and strategy: it will be the trainers visiting the centres to deliver the training course. This surely will inhibit the experiencing of their ability to orient themselves autonomously in the inclusion process and services, but ensure continuity is given to the participants.

Finland

TAIS (i): Multilingual online forum (for men)
University of Helsinki; Antti Kivijärvi, Finland
STRENGTHS [internal, positive]
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Online implementation (protected from lockdown measures). ▪ Can be used at any time and from anywhere. ▪ Easy to use and can be used anonymously. ▪ The communication was polite and respectful (no conflicts were observed). ▪ Asylum seekers had a chance to tell about their experiences and test their language skills. ▪ The forum requires only few working hours from the moderators.
WEAKNESSES [internal, negative]
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Too few participants. ▪ The topics of discussions were either too mundane (for asylum seekers) or too specific (volunteers). ▪ The discussants might have been too anonymous/impersonal. ▪ The diverse position of asylum seekers cause them to have dissimilar interests. ▪ Volunteers were not ready to respond to problems raised by asylum seekers.
OPPORTUNITIES [external, positive]
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ To provide a new platform for intergroup interaction and knowledge transmission. ▪ To bring together asylum seeking and Finnish-speaking volunteer men. ▪ To provide a platform for intergroup communication for those with limited skills in Finnish. ▪ Easy-to-use and cost-efficient way to activate asylum seekers.
THREATS [external, negative]
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Only few volunteers and participants are found/recruited. ▪ Discussions do not come alive or stay in a shallow level. ▪ Participants have difficulties in understanding each other. ▪ Communication is discriminative or strengthens existing prejudices. ▪ Plenty of technical problems are faced. ▪ Discussions are too burdensome for either participants or moderators.
Developing Actionable Strategies
Considering the above analysis, what will you adjust or do differently in the following TAIS piloting round?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ To put more effort in recruiting asylum seeker participants. ▪ To recruit asylum seekers as peer moderators. ▪ To set up a training for volunteers in order for them to get to know each other and to provide them some basic information about the everyday life of asylum seekers in Finland.

TAIS (i): Multilingual online forum (for men)

- To adjust the discussions in a way that all participants can share more things about themselves and their everyday surroundings.
- To adjust the theses of discussion in a way that more detailed/concrete issues will be discussed.

TAIS (ii): Childcare services in reception centres

Partner responsible: University of Helsinki; Martta Myllylä

STRENGTHS [internal, positive]

- Allowing asylum seeking parents with small children to use services, participate in education and rest.
- Providing children learning opportunities, structured activities and peer company instead of only being at home.
- Raising the awareness of reception centre professionals on the importance of childcare services and the vulnerabilities related to absence of it.
- Being more aware of the contexts and challenges from the service provider perspective.

WEAKNESSES [internal, negative]

- Too little resources (both personnel and operation).
- Too few hours.
- Sometimes the accessibility of the service is poor due to distances and problems in families.
- No contacts with Finnish-speaking/local children.
- Professional skills of service providers (not formal education in childcare or related topic is needed).

OPPORTUNITIES [external, positive]

- Seeing the value in childcare activities.
- Recognizing the rights of asylum seeking parents and children more thoroughly.
- Promoting the integration of asylum seeking parent and particularly children to local communities.
- Making the start of school-careers for asylum seeking children easier.
- Pushing municipalities to open up their childcare services for asylum seekers.
- Changing the legislation.

THREATS [external, negative]

- Developing childcare activities in reception centres moves the attention away from expanding the rights of asylum seeking parents and children in relation to municipal services.
- Developmental work is nullified when reception centres are closed down.
- Resources put to childcare means taking away resources from someplace else.

Developing Actionable Strategies

Considering the above analysis, what will you adjust or do differently in the following TAIS piloting round?

TAIS (ii): Childcare services in reception centres

Since the first phase of Finnish TAIS II was, due to lockdown measures, implemented from distance and included only knowledge production, no great adjustments to service provision will take place at this stage. As a next step, two reception centres included in the developmental work will be visited and their service provision will be thoroughly observed. The aim is to gain a more thorough understanding of the material, cultural and social conditions in the reception centres in order to come up with qualitative improvements in the child-care services. Moreover, during the second phase, knowledge will be produced about the possibility of guaranteeing the right in municipal early childhood education for asylum seeking families. This will be examined by interviewing personnel responsible in early childhood education and care in municipalities that are currently including asylum seeking children in day care or club activities.

Hungary

TAIS: Trajectory monitoring toolbox

Menedék - Hungarian Association for Migrants, Hungary

STRENGTHS [internal, positive]

The main asset the Hungarian TAIS can rely on is the experience of social workers at Menedék who are able to describe the history of complex case management of their HV clients in the form of a case study. These case studies were completed in Phase I, and will be considered as a primary source for the creation of vulnerability profiles.

Another asset, as well as a source for innovation is Menedék's central position in the Hungarian NGO scene concerning refugee integration. Based on earlier existing formal or informal connections, the organisation is able to bring in more expertise to identify cases relevant to the TAIS pilot project (ARU and others), and elaborate selected complex case series in a detailed, narrative case description.

Concerning knowledge and data, besides the professional experience of this 25-year-old NGO and its employees, an internal case management system is used in the social work with Menedék's clients that make it possible to validate case descriptions with activity logs.

There is also an internal supervising mechanism for social workers, therefore the objective of TAIS is to integrate project outputs and innovative strategies to the management and professional guidance of the association, as well as of stakeholders in Hungary.

WEAKNESSES [internal, negative]

Menedék as an organisation is appropriately managed, and the commitment of its employees is high. However, its sphere of action is limited due to the hostile political environment in Hungary for all initiatives focusing on refugees (see the "Threats" part).

Menedék offers services in Budapest and in three reception centres outside the capital. Access to the reception centres is somewhat unpredictable. Therefore, the TAIS must focus on BIPs living in Budapest.

Otherwise, no major internal weaknesses are found.

OPPORTUNITIES [external, positive]

Despite the low level of institutionalization of the immigrant and refugee integration policy sphere, NGOs and service providers know about each other's activities, and there is an informal (or semi-formal) network of highly committed people who work in the field.

Many times, these service providers can rely on previous good practices that were identified as points of reference for the TAIS: projects "Let's work together for integration" or "SOS Refugees" aimed at non-formal structure building, or the "Refugee Outreach" initiative reaching out for individuals and specific groups, in order to improve their access to services they need, are experiences to build upon.

TAIS: Trajectory monitoring toolbox

The TAIS idea of creating a "toolbox" for social workers and stakeholders that contains evidence-based "vulnerability profiles" as well as the description of the trajectories that these typical cases should follow in the institutional field, in order to prevent the accumulation of vulnerabilities and to reduce the isolation of vulnerable individuals, was received positively by many fellow organisations (including ARU members), so there is a high expectation in the service provider scene to get to know the outputs of the TAIS.

THREATS [external, negative]

In Hungary, the refugee and migration issue is heavily politicized. People working at NGOs or service provider institutions work in an environment where little or no help can be expected from the central government.

The weakness of service provider institutions and inter-institutional coordination in the social sphere, as well as the difficult access to many institutions and services have a negative effect on the vulnerability of the forcibly displaced.

Therefore, many times the root of the problem is that a client with complex vulnerabilities could not receive support at the right place, in the right time. Many people fall out of the scope of supportive services, because complex problems cannot be tackled by one service provider alone.

Also, in many cases the vulnerabilities or traumas are caused by the legal aspects (Dublin procedure or time spent in the transit zones waiting for the asylum application to be processed).

Concerning the role of key staff, it is true that while social workers have a good understanding of procedures in the institutional landscape, there is a high fluctuation in the field, and if a knowledgeable social worker leaves an organisation or institution, their knowledge is lost.

Developing Actionable Strategies

Considering the above analysis, what will you adjust or do differently in the following TAIS piloting round?

In Phase II, it is planned to take into account the following lessons learnt in Phase I:

The "semi-formality" of the service should not be considered as a weakness but as an asset. If being used in a reflexive way, using long-established personal connections between key stakeholders can help to resolve difficult cases of vulnerable refugees.

Self-positioning of actors (responsibility, engagement) is an important aspect of the functioning of the network, and it should be analysed carefully.

A training for social workers working at different service provider institutions should be thought out in order to ease inter-institutional communication.

Turkey

TAIS: Accessing and Participating in Basic Daily life Practices Through Monitoring
Anadolu University, Turkey
STRENGTHS [internal, positive]
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ ARU members' interest. ▪ Uniquely, local government members of ARU are keen on the product. ▪ Academic, local government, NGO-specialized bodies with experience on the issue. ▪ To name- interdisciplinary-intra and trans disciplinary. ▪ Concrete support to women, refugees, but also to local government. ▪ Allowing to cooperate and add members of specialists.
WEAKNESSES [internal, negative]
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Vulnerability to COVID-19 causes withdrawals and not full commitment. ▪ Culturally, face to face is the primary communication and close contact. ▪ Quality of meetings due to shorter meetings online. ▪ Participation and feedbacks from vulnerable groups are very limited. ▪ Extreme lock-down measures limit the available times. ▪ Access to technology and Internet for some is a serious problem.
OPPORTUNITIES [external, positive]
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Well experienced trainers. ▪ UN Women in Turkey is recently planning a similar program. ▪ All local authorities show positive and sensitive response. ▪ Interested stakeholders are joining.
THREATS [external, negative]
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Increasing Covid-19 cases. 30.000+ cases and close to 300 deaths each day create stress. ▪ Limited days and hours. ▪ Having difficulty to plan. ▪ Lacking services to FDPs (health, education, jobs and becoming visible.) ▪ More people became invisible. ▪ Centres, offices, business are either closed or rarely open.
Developing Actionable Strategies
Considering the above analysis, what will you adjust or do differently in the following TAIS piloting round?
Responsive change in recruitment model and strategy: Adapt trainings for smaller groups in more multiple training sessions due to having difficulty in setting common times.

Jordan

TAIS: Psychosocial Refugee Support Forum (PRSF)

YU – Yarmouk University; Nader Al-Refai, Amani M. Shatnawi, Aya Akkawi, Jordan

STRENGTHS [internal, positive]

1. The design and implementation of TAIS respond to vulnerability group needs. These needs were detected earlier from the previous best practices reports, Action Research Units (ARUs) and interviews held with vulnerable refugees.
2. More than 20 ARUs from different domains with highly experienced specialists in the subjects and a group of vulnerable refugees have participated in developing, designing and evaluating the TAIS. The ARUs are formed by those individuals who are working with the FDPs in the field, come from different backgrounds, and represent different organisations and NGOs.
3. YU team have accomplished the design of the training program. It has gone through many steps. The basic data used in the design process were gathered from the vulnerable refugees and ARUs during different workshops. They came together for a full-day training and brainstorming sessions to determine the training needs of the participants.
4. The TAIS allow different stakeholders to participate, especially the ones who are interested to be engaged with the local community through the understanding the laws, regulations, work permissions and how to build their own business.
5. The training content provides the participants with a real benefit that will be positively reflected on their life
6. The training program includes a set of training strategies that have a good impact on participants' lives in terms of the inclusion of the participants in discussion groups, brainstorming, constructive dialogue, and interaction between colleagues.
7. The program focuses on transferring and exchanging experiences between trainers and participants on one side, and the participants themselves on the other.
8. The program provides an opportunity for the participants to receive the necessary support during the training process.
9. Training includes attendance and follow-up records for the participants as an indicator of their commitment and acceptability of the program.

WEAKNESSES [internal, negative]

1. Finding committed ARU members was not easy and consumed a lot of time. This was because of the long process international NGOs adopted which needed the approval of participation from headquarters. In addition, such organisations have a lot of restrictions in the topics of sharing their data, procedures and programs that are presented to refugees.
2. Since the collaboration with YU team is a voluntary task, some of the interviewed ARUs did not feel obliged to commit effectively to the presented tasks.

TAIS: Psychosocial Refugee Support Forum (PRSF)

3. It took YU team two months and two workshops to divide the ARUs into five groups (The proposed TAIS has five training programs). This is due to the ARUs' different and diverse experience with refugees.
4. Due to COVID 19 restrictions, the initial planning of training program and follow-up were suspended for a short period of time. As a result, some activities were postponed and accordingly the implementation schedule was changed.
5. The participants' geographical distribution and the current global conditions may affect the rate of participation and follow-up.
6. The difference and diversity of capabilities and competences at the level of participants may affect the level of real training needs.
7. Some refugees' participants may encounter some difficulties in accessing the training programs due to the difficulty of obtaining permissions to leave their residential places (such as camps).
8. Weak electronic infrastructure in some refugees' residential places may limit their ability to participate effectively in the online implementation.
9. Poor financial capabilities of the participants may actually affect attendance and participation in activities.
10. Some refugees may not feel motivated to participate in the presented training programs because their priorities and needs may change according to current circumstances.
11. Some refugees may be illiterate when it comes to using online platforms. This may limit their access to online courses, workshops and other services that will be posted on the platform "Refugee Psychological Support System (RPSS)".
12. It is difficult to accurately determine deadlines due to the current circumstances.
13. The difficulty of predicting the next steps under the current circumstances.

OPPORTUNITIES [external, positive]

1. Developing a local model for capacity building in the context of working with refugees.
2. Building a network of local relationships with stakeholders and establishing a concept in Jordan that is concerned with the community of practice.
3. Building a platform (PRSS) for research and development that would strengthen the capacities of participants in the asylum context.
4. The presented TAIS would give valuable opportunities to different participants (ARUs, YU team, Refugees) to reach out to more communities in order to work and build strong mutual relationships.
5. The presented TAIS would make real changes in the ideology, behaviour and attitude of the participants in particular and in society in general.
6. TAIS would improve procedures in order to ensure greater participation and accessibility.
7. The presented TAIS would bring positivity and engagement to any similar strategies.
8. The presented TAIS may bring all participants to refine their skills, so they all have similar skills and knowledge in the TAIS domain. This would help reduce any weakness among participants.

THREATS [external, negative]

TAIS: Psychosocial Refugee Support Forum (PRSF)

1. The constant change in the leadership of academic institutions and the weakness of professional stability constitute a real threat to the existence and continuity of work.
2. The continuous change in the legislation governing the process of dealing with refugees may threaten the continuity of projects.
3. Challenges in maintaining some of the valuable gains acquired in the project may affect negatively on the success of the TAIS.
4. Challenges in accommodating to the current pandemic conditions may affect negatively on the success of the TAIS.
5. Some valuable ARU members may leave the program due to their job responsibility. This may affect negatively on the success of the TAIS.
6. It is difficult to have continuous financial support to ensure the TAIS sustainability.
7. Some minimal threats may appear due to organisational barriers and counterproductive responses.

Developing Actionable Strategies

Considering the above analysis, what will you adjust or do differently in the following TAIS piloting round?

Will be added later.

Lebanon

TAIS: Accessing and Participating in Basic Daily life Practices Through Monitoring

Lebanese International University, Lebanon

STRENGTHS [internal, positive]

- The design and implementation of TAIS respond to vulnerability group needs. These needs were detected earlier from the previous best practices reports, Action Research Units (ARUs) and interviews held with vulnerable refugees.
- Highly experienced specialists mainly from Bekaa and Tripoli where the heavily dense congestion of vulnerable refugees participated in developing, designing and evaluating the TAIS.
- LIU across all its 9 campuses designed and implemented the training program. The program has undergone through validation before implementation through a team of colleagues from the school of Education and the School of Pharmacy. A Google classroom was set up and where the modules are being delivered through the week.
- The TAIS allowed the program not only enrich the vulnerable people but also enhance the collective data among the community in these two sensitive areas in Lebanon.
- The Content reflected not only educational perspectives but took into consideration health priorities.
- The training program includes a set of training instructional strategies, methods and skills that should empower participants in terms of, the inclusion and not integration, through active participation with LIU students in clusters online.
- For competence outreach, the following competences were taken into consideration: cognitive, interpersonal, and intrapersonal.
- A couple of ARU members -specialized in entrepreneurship; enhanced the program design of the training content (the experts have joined after the launch of the TAIS as well as the influential support of the Former minister of Trade involved as well).
- Participation and feedbacks from vulnerable groups are very encouraging.

WEAKNESSES [internal, negative]

- Vulnerability to COVID-19, political unrest, Beirut Port explosion in Lebanon caused mitigation to full commitment.
- The massive financial crisis hitting Lebanon due to political turmoil caused even WIFI to slow down.
- Effective face-to-face meetings that usually generate high quality dissemination of meetings were replaced with shorter meetings online often interrupted with lagging of voice.
- Extreme lock-down measures limit the available times.

OPPORTUNITIES [external, positive]

- With an already strong established RESCUE Project, **The Inauguration of the Refugee Students Operational Support Unit (R-SOS)** (<https://sites.google.com/liu.edu.lb/schoolofeducation-liu/capacity-building/soed-centers-units?authuser=0>) and an entrepreneurship unit training for migrants was utilised.

TAIS: Accessing and Participating in Basic Daily life Practices Through Monitoring

- LIU with its presence across 9 campuses has provided through its stakeholders to be in close contact with NGOs.
- The TAIS is an attractive project that will be enhanced on previous projects with UNRWA gained a lot of learning opportunities in its previous engagements.
- RAISD project will benefit from an already established innovation and entrepreneurship center that could request experts to volunteer and deliver seminars. (<https://www.iecplatform.org/>)

THREATS [external, negative]

- Increasing Covid-19 cases. 3500 cases per day and 80 deaths per day.
- Lebanon has been confined to severe lockdown since January 6 and expected to March 23.
- While the formal record shows 1 million vulnerable people, the informal numbers and what all Lebanese believe is around 1.9 to 2 million. This number is half the 4 million Lebanese.
- Vulnerable people who are in irregular situation due to no documentation are exploited with low daily fare rate, sometimes causing Lebanese to be out of work.

Developing Actionable Strategies

Considering the above analysis, what will you adjust or do differently in the following TAIS piloting round?

Background information on the situation in Lebanon:

Lebanon suffered from structural inefficiencies even prior to the Syrian conflict. In 2015, an estimated 87.7% of the population was urban, and there was a significant heterogeneity between rural, urban and peri-urban areas, in terms of institutional service delivery and governance. This was further exacerbated by the conflict in Lebanon (lasting over two decades) and the political fractionalization that brought the country to a standstill.

The influx of Syrian refugees into such context dramatically deteriorated the living conditions for both refugees and host populations. The crisis increased population density in Lebanon from 400 to 520 persons per km², especially in urban areas, leading to urban congestion, competition over housing, increasing pressures on existing resources and tensions between host populations and refugees. This situation was particularly constrained in Beirut and Mount Lebanon, with only a limited number of informal settlements in the area. Most refugees in Beirut and Mount Lebanon (92%) resided in rented apartments or houses, although the comparatively high cost of living meant that many refugee families were only able to afford substandard or overcrowded accommodation. An assessment by the organisation in the target areas showed that 23% of households in Beirut and 59% in Mount Lebanon lacked basic facilities and were in need of urgent rehabilitations

Responsive change in recruitment model and strategy: Adapt trainings for smaller groups in more multiple training sessions due to having difficulty in setting common times.

www.raisd-h2020.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822688.

The information and views set out in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein.

www.raisd-h2020.eu

Del.7.2 Cross-pilot workshop Report [03/2021]

Coordinator contact: Dr. Rubén Fuentes-Fernández | Universidad Complutense de Madrid | Calle del Profesor José García Santesmases, 9. Ciudad Universitaria 28040 MADRID, Spain.
t: +34/ 91 394 7548 | e: rfuentes@ucm.es | w: www.ucm.es , grasia.fdi.ucm.es

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822688.